

Auditable Zero-Retention AI with Attestation Receipts and Differential Privacy-Bounded Learning Updates

Vincent P. Giacomo*
Epheia, Inc.

ORCID: 0009-0001-8565-9423

March 2026

Abstract

This report describes an architecture specification for running artificial intelligence (AI) large language model (LLM) workloads on regulated data with auditable non-persistence guarantees within an explicitly defined trust boundary. The core idea is to confine raw inputs to an ephemeral, Random Access Memory (RAM)-only execution environment and to emit a cryptographic attestation chain, plus a per-session “privacy receipt,” providing verifiable evidence that no non-volatile persistence occurred within the protected boundary. When learning is permitted, the system exports only differential privacy (DP) bounded numeric update artifacts (e.g., noised parameter deltas) together with an attestation-bound DP tuple. Transcripts, images, and un-noised gradients are discarded. A secure aggregator/verifier then admits updates only after validating the attestation chain and privacy budget constraints, and retains receipts only. The report introduces a threat model, trust-boundary assumptions for use with managed model endpoints, and practical design patterns for integrating these guarantees into regulated workflows. This report specifies the architecture; a reference implementation and empirical evaluation are planned as subsequent work.

Keywords: trusted execution environments, differential privacy, remote attestation, privacy receipts, non-persistence, confidential computing, regulatory compliance

1 Introduction

Healthcare and other compliance-driven sectors increasingly deploy large-scale machine learning and large language models (LLMs) for summarization, triage, and decision support [1, 2, 3]. However, the operational defaults of modern AI stacks (extensive logging, caching, replay buffers, and training corpora) make it difficult to enforce and demonstrate strict data minimization [4, 5, 6, 7]. A recurring compliance gap is one of *evidence*: even when engineers intend to avoid data retention for LLM deployments, institutions often cannot prove to auditors that protected health information (PHI), personally identifiable information (PII), and other sensitive inputs were not written to disk, snapshots, crash dumps, logs, or long-lived training sets. Encryption at rest mitigates certain threats but does not provide a verifiable guarantee of non-persistence¹ [8]; similarly, prompt-level

*Correspondence: Vincent@epheia.ai

¹Throughout this report, *non-persistence* denotes a cryptographically verifiable property: evidence that data was never written to non-volatile media. *Non-retention* denotes a policy or contractual commitment that data will not be kept beyond a stated period. The former is the technical guarantee this architecture provides; the latter is the organizational assurance it is designed to supersede.

encryption preserves confidentiality during inference but does not address non-persistence [9].

In response to this evidentiary gap in current regulated AI deployments, this report presents a systems-style technical specification of a receipt-based verification mechanism for non-persistence policies in isolated LLM runtimes, focusing on verifier-checkable evidence rather than policy statements [9, 10]. The system combines (i) RAM-only execution with write-block enforcement and egress gating [11, 12, 13, 14], (ii) hardware-rooted attestations streamed at runtime and validated as an unbroken chain [15, 16, 17, 18], (iii) optional learning constrained to DP-bounded update artifacts whose hashes and privacy parameters are bound into the attestation [19, 20] (see also patent filings [21, 22, 23]), and (iv) a secure verifier/aggregator that stores receipts at the system’s final stage [24]. Furthermore, the scope of this report is limited to the architecture and verification protocol; reference implementation and empirical evaluation are deferred to follow-on work. All security-critical normative content required to evaluate the claims in this report—including the attestation state claims schema, zeroization report schema, and additional specification details—is provided in Appendices A–D; future companion documents may expand on implementation guidance and platform-specific errata but are not required for independent review of the core architecture.

2 Background and Related Work

Confidential cloud computing and trusted execution environments (TEEs) provide isolation and attestation primitives but do not, by default, guarantee non-persistence of sensitive inputs to disks, snapshots, or logs [15, 16, 17, 25, 26]. This gap is particularly consequential for regulated LLM deployments in which the compliance requirement is not merely confidentiality of data at rest but *verifiable evidence that raw data was never durably stored*. The discussion below organizes prior work along four axes—attestation, transparency, privacy-preserving inference, and verifiable retention—and identifies the specific shortcoming each leaves unaddressed.

Remote attestation. The IETF Remote ATtestation procedureS (RATS) architecture (RFC 9334) [18] standardizes roles (Attester, Verifier, Relying Party) and evidence formats for establishing trust in a remote platform’s state. RATS enables a verifier to confirm that an enclave is running expected code and configuration, providing the foundational primitive on which the EPR-1.1 attestation chain is built. However, RATS itself is silent on data lifecycle: it attests *what code is running*, not *whether that code persisted, logged, or cached the data it processed*. A RATS attestation report alone therefore cannot serve as evidence of non-retention. The EPR-1.1 design extends the RATS model by binding write-block policy state, a monotonic freshness counter, and (when learning is enabled) a DP tuple and update hash into each attestation entry, converting a point-in-time platform measurement into a continuous non-persistence proof stream.

Transparency logs. Certificate Transparency (CT) version 2.0 (RFC 9162) [27] introduced append-only Merkle-tree logs with cryptographic inclusion and consistency proofs, enabling any observer to verify that a certificate authority’s issuance decisions are publicly auditable. CT demonstrates that transparency commitments can be made tamper-evident at scale. The limitation for our setting is one of *scope*: CT logs commit to certificate issuance events, not to data-handling lifecycle events such as ingestion, processing, and destruction of regulated inputs. EPR-1.1 borrows the structural concept of an append-only commitment (the `attestation_chain_root` and optional `transparency_merkle_root` fields) but applies it to a fundamentally different domain—session-level evidence that raw PHI/PII was confined to volatile memory, processed under attested policy, and destroyed upon teardown.

Privacy-preserving LLM inference. Li et al. [9] propose Confidential Prompting, which encrypts user prompts so that the cloud LLM provider cannot observe plaintext inputs during inference. This addresses the *confidentiality* dimension: an honest-but-curious provider learns nothing about the prompt content. It does not, however, address the *non-persistence* dimension. Even under Confidential Prompting, the provider’s infrastructure may still write ciphertexts, intermediate key-value caches, or debug logs to durable storage; the user receives no verifiable evidence that these artifacts were absent or destroyed. The EPR-1.1 architecture is complementary: the UMCEE enforces RAM-only execution and write-block policy irrespective of whether the prompt is additionally encrypted in transit, and the attestation chain provides evidence of non-persistence that Confidential Prompting’s threat model does not claim to supply.

Verifiable data retention and expungement. Panwar et al. [10] present IoT Expunge, a system for verifiable retention of IoT data that enables data owners to confirm whether their data has been deleted from a storage service. IoT Expunge is, to our knowledge, the closest prior work to the non-persistence verification goal of this report. It introduces cryptographic proofs of deletion backed by a trusted auditor, targeting scenarios in which IoT sensor data is first stored and then must be provably expunged after a retention period expires. Several structural differences distinguish EPR-1.1 from IoT Expunge:

1. **Store-then-delete vs. never-store.** IoT Expunge operates on a *store-then-delete* model: data is written to persistent storage and later proven to have been removed. The EPR-1.1 architecture enforces a *never-store* model in which write-block enforcement prevents raw data from reaching non-volatile media in the first place; the verification target is the absence of any durable write, not the completion of a retroactive deletion.
2. **Hardware-rooted vs. auditor-based attestation.** IoT Expunge’s proofs are issued by a trusted third-party auditor that inspects storage state, whereas the EPR-1.1 attestation chain is hardware-rooted (TPM, SEV-SNP, TDX, Nitro) and generated continuously from within the execution environment itself, reducing reliance on an external auditor’s access to storage internals.
3. **Machine-learning update pathway.** IoT Expunge does not address scenarios in which a learning update must leave the ephemeral boundary. When learning is enabled, the system must additionally ensure that the only artifact egressing is a DP-bounded numeric delta whose privacy parameters are cryptographically bound into the attestation—a requirement absent from IoT retention scenarios.
4. **Session-level receipt artifact.** EPR-1.1 provides a self-contained, session-level *receipt* artifact (with replay resistance, dual-signature support, and chain-root commitment) designed for automated compliance verification in regulated workflows—a packaging and verifiability layer that IoT Expunge does not specify.

Policy-based non-retention promises. Major LLM cloud providers (OpenAI, Anthropic, AWS Bedrock, Google Vertex AI, among others) offer enterprise data-handling agreements that contractually commit to zero data retention or limited retention windows [28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36]. These commitments address an important operational concern, but they are *policy-based*: the customer trusts the provider’s organizational controls, audit certifications, and contractual remedies rather than receiving per-session cryptographic evidence. The gap between a contractual non-retention

promise and a cryptographically verifiable non-persistence proof is real and, to date, largely unaddressed in the systems security literature. This work targets that gap directly.

Differential privacy and secure aggregation. Differential privacy (DP) provides formal guarantees bounding the influence of any single record on a mechanism’s output [19, 20, 37, 38], and secure aggregation protocols enable distributed update collection without exposing individual contributions [24, 39, 40]. However, standard DP and secure aggregation implementations—including those built on federated averaging [41] and its privacy-preserving extensions (see also patent filings [42, 43, 44])—assume that intermediate gradients or model updates may persist locally or at the aggregator. Theoretical analyses confirm that differentially private mechanisms can still leak information [45], and practical gradient inversion and data reconstruction attacks [46, 47] demonstrate that persisted updates can leak training data, motivating the combination of DP noise injection with strict non-persistence enforcement. The EPR-1.1 design integrates DP as an in-enclave mechanism whose parameters (mechanism type, ϵ , δ , clipping bound, sensitivity) are attested and budget-enforced by the aggregator, while the ephemeral boundary ensures that un-noised gradients and raw inputs are destroyed before any egress occurs.

Runtime attestation and auditing. TRACES [48] demonstrates TEE-based runtime auditing for embedded systems, showing that continuous attestation can detect runtime compromise. Black-box DP auditing techniques [49] provide empirical methods for verifying that a deployed mechanism satisfies its claimed privacy guarantees. The EPR-1.1 attestation pipeline draws on both lines of work: it produces a continuous (or start/stop) attestation chain analogous to runtime auditing, while the attested DP tuple enables downstream verification of privacy-budget conformance analogous to (though mechanistically distinct from) black-box DP auditing.

In summary, existing work supplies attestation primitives (RATS), transparency log structures (CT), prompt-level confidentiality (Confidential Prompting), and post-hoc verifiable deletion (IoT Ex-punge), but none provides an integrated framework that enforces RAM-only execution, produces a continuous hardware-rooted attestation chain proving non-persistence, and—when learning is enabled—constrains egress to DP-bounded update artifacts whose privacy parameters are cryptographically bound into the attestation. This is the gap that this report addresses.

3 Threat Model and Trust Assumptions

This section specifies the adversarial model, trust boundary, and residual assumptions that scope the architecture’s security guarantees. The material below consolidates and makes precise what the architecture does—and does not—defend against.

3.1 Adversary Capabilities

The threat model considers a polynomially bounded adversary \mathcal{A} who may possess one or more of the following capabilities with respect to the infrastructure that hosts an LLM session:

1. **Compromised operating-system kernel.** \mathcal{A} may control or influence the guest OS scheduler, virtual-memory subsystem, or device-driver layer. In particular, \mathcal{A} may attempt to (a) enable swap or compressed-memory paging so that volatile data is flushed to non-volatile media, (b) trigger or manufacture a kernel panic or crash dump that captures volatile state to disk, or (c) manipulate `tmpfs`/RAM-disk mount points to silently redirect writes to persistent storage.

2. **DMA-capable peripheral access.** \mathcal{A} may have logical or physical control of a PCIe device (e.g., a GPU, NIC, or storage controller) capable of issuing Direct Memory Access (DMA) transactions that bypass CPU-level write-block hooks. Without IOMMU enforcement, such a device could read enclave memory regions or write enclave data directly to an NVMe controller.
3. **Attestation replay and splicing.** \mathcal{A} may capture legitimate attestation packets from a prior session and attempt to replay them, or splice attestation sub-chains from two independent sessions to fabricate a valid-looking chain for a session that actually violated policy. \mathcal{A} may also attempt to forge or strip individual heartbeat entries to mask a gap in the monotonic freshness counter.
4. **Malicious or curious aggregator.** When learning is enabled, \mathcal{A} may control the secure aggregator endpoint and attempt to reconstruct training data or raw inputs from the received DP-noised update artifacts $\hat{\Delta}$. This includes gradient-inversion attacks, membership-inference probes, and data-reconstruction techniques that exploit insufficiently noised or unclipped updates [46, 50, 47].
5. **Network-level observation.** \mathcal{A} may observe all traffic between the UMCEE, the Egress Gate, the model execution endpoint, and the aggregator. Mutual TLS mitigates content exposure, but traffic-analysis side channels (timing, message sizes) are in scope for future work and are not fully addressed by the current design.

3.2 Trusted Components

The following components are assumed to be correct (i.e., they faithfully execute their specified behavior). The security argument degrades if any of these assumptions is violated. Table 1 summarizes these components and the justification for each assumption.

Table 1: Trusted components and their assumptions.

Component	Trust Assumption	Justification
Hardware root of trust	The CPU’s attestation key and measurement registers (TPM PCRs, SEV-SNP VCEK, TDX SEAM, Nitro NSM) are tamper-resistant and faithfully report the enclave’s code identity and configuration.	Industry-standard TEE threat models [15, 16, 17].
UMCEE measured code image	The code loaded into the UMCEE—including the Write-Block Policy Engine (WBPE), Real-Time Attestation Module (RTAM), Shadow-Storage Controller, and Detonation Handler—is the code whose measurement is committed in <code>platform_report.image_digest</code> . A reproducible-build pipeline and an allow-list reference (<code>platform_report.allowlist_ref</code>) enable external verification.	Reproducible builds reduce the trust surface to the build toolchain and the allow-list governance process.
Hypervisor / secure monitor (dual-signature mode)	When <code>signature_policy="dual"</code> , the hypervisor or secure monitor that co-signs attestation digests holds its signing key in a trust domain independent of the enclave. Simultaneous compromise of both domains is out of scope.	Dual-signature attestation (Section 4, Table 2) requires two independent compromises.
Cryptographic primitives	SHA-256 (or SHA3-256), ECDSA P-256/P-384, AES-GCM, and HMAC-SHA-256 are computationally secure for the lifetime of a session and the retention period of receipts.	Standard cryptographic assumptions; post-quantum migration is noted as future work.

3.3 Verified (Untrusted-but-Checked) Components

The following components are *not* trusted by default; instead, the architecture provides mechanisms for an external verifier or the Egress Gate to check their behavior:

- **Guest OS and storage subsystem.** The WBPE intercepts all non-volatile I/O system calls and hypervisor I/O exits. The IOMMU policy blocks DMA writes from untrusted peripherals. These enforcement mechanisms are measured into the attestation, so a verifier can confirm they were active throughout the session. A compromised OS that attempts to write to disk will be blocked; if the block is circumvented (e.g., by exploiting a WBPE bug), the attestation chain will reflect the policy violation or the heartbeat will cease, triggering egress refusal.
- **Attestation chain integrity.** The Egress Gate and any external verifier validate the full attestation chain: monotonic freshness-counter continuity (no gaps, no duplicates), cadence compliance (no heartbeat interval exceeding τ in periodic mode), signature verification against known trust anchors, and nonce binding (preventing cross-session replay). A spliced or replayed chain will fail at least one of these checks.

- **DP-noised update artifacts.** The secure aggregator independently recomputes $H(\hat{\Delta})$ over the received payload bytes and matches the result against the `update_digest` committed in the terminal attestation. It then validates the attested DP tuple $\Gamma = (\text{mech}, \varepsilon, \delta, C, S, \Pi)$, where Π denotes the remaining mechanism-specific parameters (e.g., noise scale σ or b , noise multiplier, and accountant configuration), against the mechanism-specific calibration rule and the remaining global privacy budget. An update that was insufficiently noised, unclipped, or that would exceed the cumulative budget is rejected before any merge occurs.

3.4 The Trust Boundary, the Non-Persistence Guarantee, and the Model-Endpoint Interface

3.4.1 Properly Scoped Security Guarantees

Every meaningful security guarantee is conditional on stated assumptions and scoped to a defined boundary. TLS guarantees channel confidentiality and integrity—under the assumption that the certificate chain is valid and the cryptographic primitives are secure—but makes no claim about what the server application does with the plaintext after decryption. A TEE guarantees isolation and attested code identity—under standard hardware root-of-trust assumptions—but does not guarantee that the code running inside is free of logic bugs. The rigor of a security architecture is measured not by whether it qualifies its guarantees, but by whether the assumptions are explicit, the boundary is precisely defined, and the evidence is independently verifiable.

The Epheia architecture follows this principle. The UMCEE defines the trust boundary. Within it, the system enforces non-persistence through layered runtime mechanisms and produces a continuous, hardware-rooted, independently verifiable cryptographic evidence chain proving that enforcement was active and unbroken for the entirety of the session. The qualification “within the defined trust boundary” is not a concession—it is the architecturally correct way to state a security guarantee whose assumptions and scope are made fully explicit.

3.4.2 What the Architecture Enforces Within the Boundary

Within the UMCEE, non-persistence is not a policy aspiration; it is a runtime-enforced invariant backed by four complementary mechanisms: kernel/hypervisor-level write-block interception (addressing Adversary Capability 1, Section 3.1), DMA isolation via IOMMU policy (Adversary Capability 2), sub-swap-interval shredding of RAM-backed temporary files with per-session encryption, and hardware-assisted zeroization at session termination. These mechanisms collectively ensure that raw input data, intermediate tensors, and un-noised gradients are never written to non-volatile storage and are destroyed in volatile memory at session end. Section 5 specifies each mechanism in full detail.

3.4.3 What the Architecture Proves About Enforcement

Enforcement alone is necessary but not sufficient for a compliance-grade guarantee. The distinguishing contribution of this architecture is that enforcement is continuously attested by a hardware-rooted, tamper-evident, independently verifiable evidence chain. A Real-Time Attestation Module (RTAM) periodically samples enforcement-layer state, hashes each sample into a state digest signed by the processor’s hardware root of trust, and chains entries via a strictly monotonic freshness counter. Optional dual-signature mode requires two cryptographically independent trust domains to co-sign each digest, and a per-session freshness nonce bound into every platform evidence blob

prevents cross-session replay. At termination, the attestation commits to a proof-of-zero (zeroization report and teardown digests). The EPR-1.1 privacy receipt binds the full attestation chain, policy configuration, egress decision, and (when learning is enabled) the DP tuple into a single signed artifact that any external party can independently verify.

The result is that a compliance team, auditor, or regulator presented with an EPR-1.1 receipt can independently verify—without trusting any party’s verbal or contractual assurance—that for a specific session: (i) the attested code image was loaded, (ii) write-block enforcement was active and unbroken from instantiation through termination, (iii) no heartbeat was missed, (iv) volatile memory was zeroized, and (v) when learning occurred, the exported update satisfied the declared DP parameters. This moves regulated AI compliance from a trust-based posture (“trust our non-retention policy”) to an evidence-based posture (“verify our non-retention proof”). The normative 16-step verification protocol is specified in Section 6.

3.4.4 The Model-Endpoint Interface

With the guarantee and its scope established, it is now possible to state precisely how the model execution endpoint (Figure 1, “Model Execution Endpoint (policy-selected)”) relates to the trust boundary.

Prompt minimization at the boundary edge. Before any data crosses the trust boundary to reach the model execution endpoint, the UMCEE performs prompt minimization and tokenization under the session’s policy. This reduces the information content of the outbound request to the minimum necessary for inference and encrypts it for transit over a mutually authenticated channel. The degree of minimization is a policy parameter committed in `policy_state_digest`.

The model endpoint’s position is a deployment-level policy decision. The model execution endpoint may be deployed in one of two configurations, and the choice is an explicit, auditable policy decision recorded in the attestation:

1. **Inside the trust boundary (extended-boundary deployment).** The model endpoint itself runs within a UMCEE or TEE instance, with its own attestation entries included in the session’s attestation chain using a distinct `component` label (e.g., “`inference-enclave`”). In this configuration, the non-persistence guarantee and its cryptographic evidence extend end-to-end: from input ingestion, through prompt minimization, through inference, through post-processing, to egress and teardown. The receipt reflects the extended boundary through the additional attestation entries.
2. **Outside the trust boundary (boundary-edge deployment).** The model endpoint is a managed API service (e.g., a cloud provider’s LLM endpoint operating under contractual non-retention terms or a Business Associate Agreement). In this configuration, the UMCEE’s enforced and attested non-persistence guarantee covers everything up to and after the inference call—prompt minimization and encryption before, post-processing and egress gating after—while the endpoint itself is governed by its operational and contractual commitments. Prompt minimization reduces the data exposed at this boundary to tokenized, policy-reduced inputs rather than raw PHI/PII.

These configurations represent a continuum: the attestation chain’s support for multiple `component` labels allows a managed API provider that deploys inference inside a TEE to contribute its own

attestation entries to the session chain, extending the trust boundary without modifying the EPR-1.1 receipt schema. Section 7 develops this progressive trust-boundary extension into a concrete integration proposal.

Egress gating is independent of endpoint placement. Regardless of the model endpoint’s position, the Egress Gate validates the full attestation chain before releasing the encrypted response to the regulated client. A model endpoint—whether compromised, misconfigured, or simply outside the trust boundary—that returns a manipulated or policy-violating response does not bypass the attestation or receipt mechanism. The response must pass through UMCEE post-processing and egress validation before reaching the data sink.

3.4.5 Design Rationale

Scoping the cryptographic non-persistence guarantee to an explicitly defined and auditable trust boundary is a deliberate architectural choice grounded in established security-engineering practice. Every security mechanism—from TLS to TEEs to differential privacy—defines a scope within which its guarantees hold and makes assumptions explicit outside that scope. A system that claimed universal non-persistence across all infrastructure without qualification would be making an unfalsifiable assertion rather than a verifiable guarantee.

The Epheia design instead provides a precisely defined boundary (the UMCEE) within which non-persistence is enforced and attested, layered enforcement mechanisms (Section 5), a continuous hardware-rooted evidence chain verified by a normative protocol (Section 6), and an extensible architecture that allows deployers to widen the trust boundary when their compliance requirements demand it (Section 7). An auditable record (`policy_state_digest`) captures exactly where the boundary was drawn for each session. This combination—enforcement, evidence, and explicit scoping—constitutes an evidence-backed guarantee of non-persistence within the defined trust boundary, under the standard TEE and cryptographic assumptions stated in Sections 3.2 and 3.5.

3.5 Residual Risks and Out-of-Scope Threats

The following threats are acknowledged but not fully mitigated by the current design:

- **Cold-boot and physical memory-residue attacks.** After the Detonation Handler zeroes RAM, electromagnetic or cryogenic techniques may recover residual charge patterns. Hardware-fuse solutions (e.g., disabling SPD EEPROM) and memory-encryption schemes (e.g., AMD SME/SEV memory encryption with key destruction) reduce but do not eliminate this risk.
- **Side-channel leakage.** Timing, power-analysis, and micro-architectural side channels (e.g., cache-line attacks against SGX [51]) may leak partial information about inputs processed inside the UMCEE. The architecture does not claim resistance to micro-architectural side channels; deployments in high-assurance environments should layer additional mitigations (e.g., constant-time code paths, cache partitioning).
- **Traffic-analysis of encrypted channels.** An observer who sees the encrypted traffic between the UMCEE and the model endpoint or between the UMCEE and the regulated client may infer metadata (prompt length, response length, session duration). Padding and traffic-shaping countermeasures are deployment-specific and are not specified by EPR-1.1.

- **Compromised hardware root of trust.** A supply-chain attack that subverts the CPU’s attestation key material invalidates all downstream guarantees. This is a shared assumption with the broader TEE ecosystem and is mitigated by platform vendor key-provisioning ceremonies and certificate transparency logs [27].
- **Quantum adversaries.** The cryptographic primitives used in EPR-1.1 (ECDSA, SHA-256) are not post-quantum secure. Migration to post-quantum signature schemes (e.g., ML-DSA/Dilithium) is noted as future work; the receipt schema’s algorithm-qualified fields (`receipt.signature`, `attestations[*].signatures[*].sig`) are designed to accommodate algorithm agility.

4 Architecture Overview

4.1 System Model

As shown in Figure 1, the architecture defines an execution boundary, the Universal Memory-Confined Execution Environment (UMCEE). The UMCEE is implemented as a trusted execution environment (TEE), protected virtual machine (VM), container, or equivalent isolation domain. The UMCEE is instantiated per LLM session and is configured to keep all raw inputs and intermediate tensors in volatile memory only. Furthermore, the UMCEE enforces a no-write policy to non-volatile media (disk, object storage, snapshots, crash dumps) using a write-block policy engine and shadow-storage controls for any RAM-backed temporary files. Complementing the UMCEE is a real-time attestation module that signs state measurements (including policy configuration and freshness counters) to produce an attestation stream. LLM outputs are released only if an external egress gate verifies an unbroken attestation chain for the session.

Figure 1: Policy-governed, attested, ephemeral execution pipeline for regulated LLM inference with optional DP-bounded learning.

4.2 Privacy Receipt Verification

An LLM privacy receipt acts like a verifiable audit slip: it lets an outside reviewer check that an AI session ran inside the intended locked-down environment, followed the stated policies, and only released outputs if the evidence chain stayed intact, while not storing the sensitive inputs themselves. This section specifies the “Epheia Privacy Receipt-1.1 (EPR-1.1),” a receipt schema that adds receipt-level tamper evidence and replay resistance (`receipt_digest/receipt_signature` + nonce), explicit chain continuity via a monotonic freshness counter (and optional cadence τ), optional dual signatures over an identical state digest, proof-of-zero termination binding, and a mechanism-specific DP tuple gamma (Γ) that is cryptographically bound to the attested update hash.

Table 2: EPR-1.1 receipt fields — selected summary. This table lists the principal fields to support architectural discussion in the main body; it is not exhaustive. Fields present in the full normative schema (Table 4, Appendix A) but omitted here for brevity are listed in a summary row at the end of this table. Table 4 is authoritative for all field-level requirements, encoding constraints, and DoS-prevention recommendations. Req.: Y = required; O = optional; C = conditional.

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Brief description
Receipt identity, freshness, tamper-evidence			
version	string	Y	Must equal "EPR-1.1".
receipt_profile	string	Y	Packaging profile: "EPR-1.1-compact" or "EPR-1.1-full".
receipt_id	string	Y	Globally unique receipt identifier.
issued_at	date-time	Y	Receipt issuance timestamp.
session_id	string	Y	Unique session identifier.
action	string	Y	Action label (e.g., "chat").
freshness.nonce	string	Y	CSPRNG replay-prevention challenge (≥ 16 bytes).
receipt_digest	string	Y	Digest over canonicalized receipt (excl. digest & signature fields).
receipt_signature	string	Y	Domain-separated signature over <code>receipt_digest</code> .
receipt_kid	string	O	Key identifier for <code>receipt_signature</code> .
Egress decision + output binding			
decision	string	Y	Egress Gate verdict: "RELEASE" or "WITHHOLD".
response_ciphertext_digest	string	C	SHA-256 of released ciphertext (required iff RELEASE).
Attestation chain			
signature_policy	string	Y	Signature cardinality: "dual" or "single".
attestation_mode	string	Y	Emission mode: "periodic" or "start_stop".
attestation_policy.tau_ms	integer	C	Heartbeat cadence threshold τ (ms).
attestation_chain_root	string	Y	Commitment over ordered state-digest chain.
attestation_bundle_digest	string	C	Digest of canonical attestation bundle.
attestation_bundle_ref	uri	O	URI for fetching the attestation bundle.
attestations	array	C	Ordered attestation entries (start \rightarrow heartbeats \rightarrow stop).
attestations[*].kind	string	Y	Attestation phase: "start", "heartbeat", or "stop".

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued from previous page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Brief description
attestations[*].ts	date-time	Y	Advisory timestamp (not authoritative for ordering).
attestations[*].freshness_counter	integer	Y	Sole authoritative ordering field; strictly increasing.
attestations[*].state_digest	string	Y	Digest of canonical attested state claims.
attestations[*].evidence_format	string	Y	Platform evidence format identifier (e.g., "amd-sev-snp-report").
attestations[*].evidence_digest	string	Y	Digest of platform attestation evidence blob.
attestations[*].evidence	string	O	Inline base64url evidence bytes.
attestations[*].evidence_ref	uri	O	URI for fetching evidence bytes.
attestations[*].signatures	array	Y	Signature(s) over <code>state_digest</code> ; cardinality per <code>signature_policy</code> .
attestations[*].signatures[*].sig	string	Y	Domain-separated signature value.
certs	array	C	Certificate bag (PEM); required for full profile.
key_material_by_kid	object	C	Key-ID \rightarrow verification material mapping.
Platform measurement report			
platform_report.image_digest	string	Y	SHA-256 of measured runtime image.
platform_report.cadence_ms	integer	C	Reporting cadence (ms); required if periodic mode.
Policy binding			
network_policy	array	Y	Declared policy tokens (e.g., ["self-origin"]).
policy_state_digest	string	Y	Digest commitment to complete session policy configuration.
Differential privacy tuple Γ			
dp_tuple.enabled	boolean	Y	<code>true</code> iff learning update produced; else inference-only.
dp_tuple.mech	string	C	Mechanism: gaussian, laplace, zcdp-gaussian, or rdp-subsampled-gaussian.
dp_tuple.adjacency	string	C	Neighboring-dataset definition: <code>add_remove</code> or <code>replace_one</code> .
dp_tuple.clip.{norm, bound}	string	C	Clipping norm and per-record bound $C > 0$.
dp_tuple.sensitivity.{norm, bound, source}	string	C	Sensitivity $S > 0$, norm, and derivation source.
dp_tuple.guarantee.{type, epsilon, delta, rho}	string	C	Privacy guarantee (ϵ -DP, (ϵ, δ) -DP, ρ -zCDP, or RDP).
dp_tuple.accountant.{type, sample_rate, rounds}	varies	C	RDP accountant parameters (required for RDP mechanism).
dp_tuple.calibration.rule	string	C	Calibration/accounting rule identifier.
dp_tuple.params.{sigma, b, noise_multiplier}	decimal	C	Mechanism-specific noise parameters.
dp_tuple.rdp_curve	array	O	Optional explicit RDP curve points.
dp_tuple.tuple_digest	string	C	Digest of canonicalized DP tuple.
Update / teardown commitments			
update_digest	string	C	CBOR-encoded commitment to DP-noised update $\hat{\Delta}$.
zeroization_report_digest	string	Y	Commitment to post-teardown zeroization report.
teardown_digest	string	Y	Commitment to teardown/finalization report.

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued from previous page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Brief description	
transcript_commitment	object	Y	Channel transcript commitment (not raw transcript).	
transcript_commitment.scheme	string	Y	" <code>hmac-sha256</code> " (recommended) or " <code>salted-sha256</code> ".	
transcript_commitment.value	string	Y	64-char hex commitment value.	
transcript_commitment.key_id	string	C	HMAC key identifier (required for <code>hmac-sha256</code> scheme).	
transcript_commitment.salt	string	C	Random salt (required for <code>salted-sha256</code> scheme).	
External inputs / connectors				
connector_selection	array	Y	Hash-bound list of external inputs (may be empty).	
connector_selection[*].name	string	Y	Connector artifact name.	
connector_selection[*].sha256	string	Y	SHA-256 digest of the connector artifact.	
Transparency + verification endpoint				
transparency_merkle_root	string/null	Y	Transparency commitment (required key; value may be null).	
verifier_url	uri	Y	Receipt verification endpoint URL.	
<i>Additional fields omitted from this summary (see Table 4 for full definitions)</i>				
<i>Required (Y):</i>		—	Y	Component label, platform identifier, signature role, and platform namespace.
<code>attestations[*].component,</code> <code>attestations[*].platform,</code> <code>attestations[*].signatures[*].role,</code> <code>platform_report.platform</code>				
<i>Optional (O):</i>		—	O	Runtime configuration digest and reproducible-build allow-list reference.
<code>platform_report.config_digest,</code> <code>platform_report.allowlist_ref</code>				

5 Enforcement Mechanisms

Section 4.1 states that the UMCEE enforces a no-write policy to non-volatile media using a write-block policy engine and shadow-storage controls. This section specifies the concrete enforcement layers that realize that guarantee. Four complementary mechanisms operate simultaneously: kernel/hypervisor-level write-block interception, shadow-storage management with per-session encryption, DMA isolation via IOMMU policy, and a deterministic shred scheduler whose timing bound is derived from the host paging interval.

5.1 Write-Block Policy Enforcement

The Write-Block Policy Engine (WBPE) intercepts every storage-class I/O operation before it can reach non-volatile media. Interception occurs at one or more of three layers, depending on the deployment's isolation model:

System-call hooking. On Linux-based deployments, the WBPE registers a kernel security module (LSM) hook on inode permission checks. When a write or memory-map request targets an inode backed by a non-volatile block device, the hook returns `-EPERM`, preventing the operation from proceeding. An illustrative LSM hook is:

```

static int wbpe_inode_permission(struct inode *inode, int mask)
{
    if (is_nv_device(inode) && (mask & MAY_WRITE))
        return -EPERM;
    return 0;
}

```

where `is_nv_device()` consults a device classification table populated at UMCEE instantiation from the policy manifest injected by the Session Orchestrator (Figure 1).

Hypervisor I/O-exit trapping. When the UMCEE runs as a protected VM (e.g., under AMD SEV-SNP or Intel TDX), the hypervisor intercepts guest I/O exits targeting non-volatile controllers (NVMe, SATA, virtio-blk backed by persistent images). The hypervisor injects a fault or silently discards the write, depending on policy. This layer is defense-in-depth: it catches writes that a compromised guest kernel might attempt to issue below the LSM layer.

Block-device driver interception. For container-based deployments where a full hypervisor trap is unavailable, the WBPE may alternatively operate as a stacking block-device driver or device-mapper target that interposes on the I/O path. Write BIOS destined for non-volatile backing stores are rejected at the driver level before reaching the storage controller.

All three interception points feed events into the attestation pipeline: each denied write increments a violation counter whose current value is included in the next attestation digest (bound into `attestations[*].state_digest` per Table 2). This ensures that even unsuccessful write attempts are visible to the external verifier.

5.2 Shadow-Storage Controls

Certain operating-system subsystems and application runtimes require a writable filesystem interface (e.g., for temporary files, Unix domain sockets, or lock files). The UMCEE satisfies these requirements through *shadow storage*: RAM-backed filesystems (such as Linux `tmpfs` or an explicit ramdisk) that present standard POSIX block-device semantics but reside entirely in volatile memory.

A Shadow-Storage Controller (SSC) manages these mounts with two additional protections:

- **Per-session encryption.** Each shadow-storage mount is encrypted with an AES-256-GCM key generated at UMCEE instantiation and held exclusively in CPU registers or enclave-protected memory. The key is never written to disk or firmware NVRAM. This prevents recovery of shadow-storage contents from a memory dump obtained after key destruction.
- **Timed zeroization.** On file close—or at a configurable heartbeat interval Δt_{shred} (default ≤ 50 ms)—the SSC overwrites the file’s physical pages with pseudorandom data via `memset_s` or equivalent side-channel-resistant primitives, then removes the corresponding page-table mappings. Each shred event’s page list is hashed and included in the next attestation packet (see Section 5.4), so the external verifier can confirm that no shadow-storage content persisted beyond the shred window.

The critical design invariant is that the SSC’s shred window is strictly shorter than the interval at which the host operating system’s memory manager could page shadow-storage contents to a swap device—even if swap is nominally disabled, since certain kernel code paths (e.g., hibernation, crash-dump collection) can still force writeback. Section 5.4 formalizes this bound.

5.3 DMA Isolation

Write-block enforcement at the system-call and hypervisor layers does not protect against device-initiated Direct Memory Access (DMA) transfers. A malicious or misconfigured PCIe device (e.g., a NIC with RDMA capability, or a compromised NVMe controller) could read UMCEE memory regions and write their contents to non-volatile storage, bypassing all software-layer hooks.

The UMCEE therefore requires an active IOMMU policy (Intel VT-d, AMD-Vi, or ARM SMMU) that restricts DMA mappings for the UMCEE’s physical memory pages. Specifically:

- Only devices explicitly enumerated in the policy manifest (e.g., an attested GPU for model inference) receive IOMMU page-table entries granting read access to UMCEE memory regions.
- No device receives write access to NVMe or other non-volatile controller command queues from UMCEE-mapped memory. DMA write requests from untrusted devices to NVMe submission queues are blocked by the IOMMU before reaching the storage controller.
- The IOMMU configuration (device-map tables) is included in the state measured by the attestation module. Any runtime modification to DMA mappings is reflected in the next attestation digest, making unauthorized DMA path changes detectable by the verifier.

This layer is particularly important for cloud deployments where the UMCEE shares a physical host with other tenants: without IOMMU enforcement, a co-tenant’s device-passthrough configuration could, in principle, initiate DMA reads of the UMCEE’s address space.

5.4 Shred Timing Guarantee

The deterministic shred scheduler bounds the maximum interval during which any sensitive data exists in readable form within shadow storage. Let T_{swap} denote the host operating system’s effective paging interval—i.e., the minimum time between successive scans of the page-replacement algorithm that could select a shadow-storage page for writeback. The UMCEE enforces:

$$\Delta t_{\text{shred}} \leq \frac{T_{\text{swap}}}{2} \tag{1}$$

This bound ensures that even in the worst case—where a shred cycle completes immediately *after* the paging daemon’s scan, and the next scan occurs at the earliest possible moment—the data will have been overwritten before any paging daemon could select it for eviction to a swap device. Concretely: the maximum delay between a page being written and the next shred is Δt_{shred} ; the minimum delay until the next paging scan is T_{swap} . Because $\Delta t_{\text{shred}} \leq T_{\text{swap}}/2 < T_{\text{swap}}$, the shred always completes strictly before the next scan, regardless of phase alignment between the two schedulers.

When host-level swap is disabled (the recommended configuration for UMCEE hosts), T_{swap} is undefined in the conventional sense. In this case, the shred window defaults to a fixed policy parameter W (recommended $W \leq 50$ ms), which guards against residual-data exposure from crash dumps, hibernation paths, or cold-boot attacks on DRAM remanence.

The shred scheduler’s current window Δt_{shred} (or W) and the timestamp of the most recent completed shred cycle are committed into the attestation state claims (via `policy_state_digest`), enabling the verifier to confirm that the shred bound was maintained throughout the session. In periodic attestation mode, the cadence threshold τ (Table 2, `attestation_policy.tau_ms`) should satisfy $\tau \leq 2 \times \Delta t_{\text{shred}}$ to ensure that at least one attestation is emitted per shred cycle.

5.5 Pluggable Erasure at Teardown

At session termination, the UMCEE’s Detonation Handler executes a full erasure of the volatile-memory region allocated to the session. The erasure method is selected per policy and may be one of:

1. **Physical overwrite.** The handler iterates over the allocated physical page range using hardware-assisted bulk-zero instructions (e.g., x86 `REP STOSB` with Enhanced `REP MOVSB/STOSB`, or ARM DC `ZVA`), then verifies the zero state via a read-back pass.
2. **Cryptographic key destruction.** If the UMCEE’s memory was encrypted with a session-scoped key (as in AMD SEV-SNP’s per-VM encryption or the SSC’s per-mount AES key), destroying the key renders the ciphertext unrecoverable. Key destruction is performed by overwriting the key material in CPU registers or secure key storage, followed by a register-barrier instruction to prevent speculative reuse.
3. **Hybrid.** Both physical overwrite and key destruction are performed, providing defense-in-depth against partial failures of either method.

Regardless of method, the Detonation Handler emits a final termination attestation whose state claims include `zeroization_report_digest` (Table 2), committing to the erasure procedure executed, the memory regions claimed wiped, and the wipe algorithm identifier (e.g., `"memset_s_v1"`, `"key_destroy_aes256"`). The `teardown_digest` field in the receipt (Table 2) binds this proof into the session’s EPR-1.1 receipt, providing the external verifier with a complete chain of evidence from instantiation through destruction.

6 Verification Protocol

The EPR-1.1 receipt schema (Table 2) specifies field-level semantics and constraints, but a conformant verifier must execute those constraints in a specific order to avoid accepting a receipt whose individual fields parse correctly yet whose cross-field bindings are inconsistent. This section presents the normative verification algorithm as a single coherent procedure. An implementation that reorders steps *may* accept receipts that a correctly ordered verifier would reject (e.g., checking DP calibration before confirming the attestation chain is unbroken could allow a forged chain to carry a valid-looking DP tuple).

6.1 Verification Algorithm

A verifier receiving an EPR-1.1 receipt R and, when `receipt_profile="EPR-1.1-full"`, its inline attestation and certificate material (or, for `"EPR-1.1-compact"`, access to the external attestation bundle), executes the following steps. Any step that fails **MUST** cause immediate rejection; the verifier **SHOULD** record the failing step identifier for audit.

Algorithm 1 — `VERIFYEPR11(R , expected_policy_digest, trust_anchors, [privacy_budget_state])`

Input: Receipt JSON object R ; expected policy-state digest; set of trust-anchor certificates/public keys; optional aggregator-side privacy-budget state (for learning-enabled sessions).

Output: `ACCEPT` or `REJECT(step, reason)`.

Step 1. Structural parse and version gate.

Parse R as JSON. Verify $R.version = \text{“EPR-1.1”}$. Verify all required (Y) fields are present per Table 2 given $R.receipt_profile$, $R.attestation_mode$, and $R.dp_tuple.enabled$. Reject on any missing required field or unknown version.

Step 2. Nonce freshness and entropy check.

Decode $R.freshness.nonce$ from base64url to $nonce_bytes$. Verify $|nonce_bytes| \geq 16$ (128-bit minimum entropy). Implementations **SHOULD** also verify $|nonce_bytes| \leq 64$ to prevent DoS. If the verifier issued the nonce as a challenge, confirm $nonce_bytes$ matches the issued challenge; if not, reject as replay or mismatch.

Step 3. Recompute and verify receipt digest.

Let R' be a copy of R with the fields `receipt_digest` and `receipt_signature` removed (all other fields, including `receipt_kid` if present, are retained). Canonicalize R' via RFC 8785 (JCS), encode to UTF-8 bytes, and compute:

$$digest = \langle hash\text{-}alg \rangle : \text{hex}(H(\text{JCS}(R'))))$$

where $\langle hash\text{-}alg \rangle$ is the algorithm prefix declared in $R.receipt_digest$ (e.g., `sha-256`). Reject if $digest \neq R.receipt_digest$.

Step 4. Verify receipt signature.

Construct the domain-separated signing input:

$$sig_input = \text{UTF8}(\text{“EPR-1.1/receipt_digest/”}) \parallel \text{UTF8}(R.receipt_digest) \quad (2)$$

Resolve the public key for verification: if $R.receipt_kid$ is present, look up the corresponding entry in $R.key_material_by_kid$ (full profile) or via configured trust anchors (compact profile); validate the certificate path to a trust anchor in $trust_anchors$. Parse the algorithm prefix from $R.receipt_signature$ (e.g., `ecdsa-p384-sha384`), decode the signature bytes, and verify the signature over sig_input . Reject on mismatch or untrusted key.

Step 5. Validate attestation chain structure and bookending.

Obtain the attestation array: inline from $R.attestations$ (full profile) or by fetching from $R.attestation_bundle_ref$ and verifying it hashes to $R.attestation_bundle_digest$ (compact profile). Let the ordered array be $A[0..n-1]$. Verify:

- (a) $A[0].kind = \text{“start”}$ and $A[n-1].kind = \text{“stop”}$.
- (b) If $R.attestation_mode = \text{“start_stop”}$: the array contains exactly two entries ($n = 2$) with kinds `“start”` and `“stop”` only.
- (c) If $R.attestation_mode = \text{“periodic”}$: intermediate entries ($A[1..n-2]$) have `kind = “heartbeat”`. Enforce $n \leq maxItems$ (recommended $\leq 10,000$).

Step 6. Verify monotonic freshness counter and continuity.

For each adjacent pair ($A[i]$, $A[i+1]$):

- (a) Verify $A[i+1].\text{freshness_counter} > A[i].\text{freshness_counter}$ (strict monotonicity).
Reject on duplicate or non-increasing values.
- (b) If $R.\text{attestation_mode} = \text{"periodic"}$: verify

$$A[i+1].\text{freshness_counter} - A[i].\text{freshness_counter} = 1$$

(no gaps). Any gap indicates a missed heartbeat; **MUST** reject (egress refusal).

- (c) If $R.\text{attestation_mode} = \text{"start_stop"}$: the gap magnitude between start and stop is unconstrained, but the stop counter **MUST** be strictly greater.

Optionally apply timestamp-range plausibility checks on $A[*].\text{ts}$ as an auditing heuristic (see Table 2, $\text{attestations}[*].\text{ts}$); timestamp violations alone **SHOULD** be logged as warnings, not hard failures, unless deployment policy escalates them.

Step 7. Verify each attestation entry’s signatures against signature_policy.

For each entry $A[i]$:

- (a) Construct:

$$\text{sig_input}_i = \text{UTF8}(\text{"EPR-1.1/state_digest/"}) \parallel \text{UTF8}(A[i].\text{state_digest})$$

- (b) If $R.\text{signature_policy} = \text{"dual"}$: verify $A[i].\text{signatures}$ contains ≥ 2 entries with distinct `role` values, including at least one `"enclave"` and at least one `"hypervisor"` or `"monitor"`. Verify that the two signing keys are rooted in independent certificate chains (independent trust domains). Verify each $A[i].\text{signatures}[*].\text{sig}$ over sig_input_i using the key resolved by $A[i].\text{kid}$ or the role-to-key mapping against trust_anchors .
- (c) If $R.\text{signature_policy} = \text{"single"}$: verify ≥ 1 signature. Flag as reduced-assurance.
- (d) Reject on any signature verification failure, missing role, or trust-domain violation.

Step 8. Recompute attestation_chain_root and compare.

Form the JSON array of strings:

$$[A[0].\text{state_digest}, A[1].\text{state_digest}, \dots, A[n-1].\text{state_digest}]$$

Canonicalize via RFC 8785 (JCS), encode to UTF-8 bytes, and compute the hash. Verify it matches $R.\text{attestation_chain_root}$. Reject on mismatch.

Note: This is a flat (non-Merkle) commitment; the full chain must be buffered before verification.

Step 9. Verify platform evidence binding (nonce + state_digest).

For each entry $A[i]$ where platform evidence is available (inline via $A[i].\text{evidence}$, by reference via $A[i].\text{evidence_ref}$, or out-of-band):

- (a) Decode/fetch evidence_bytes . Verify $\text{sha256}(\text{evidence_bytes}) = A[i].\text{evidence_digest}$. Enforce per-format size limits.
- (b) Determine the binding convention from $A[i].\text{evidence_format}$ (see Table 2, platform-specific profiles):

- **AMD SEV-SNP / Intel TDX:** Extract the 64-byte `REPORT_DATA` field. Verify:

$$\text{REPORT_DATA} = \text{sha256}(\text{nonce_bytes}) \parallel \text{state_digest_bytes}$$

where `state_digest_bytes` is the raw 32-byte hash extracted from `A[i].state_digest` (strip the `sha256:` prefix and decode hex).

- **AWS Nitro:** Extract variable-length `user_data`. Verify:

$$\text{user_data} = \text{nonce_bytes} \parallel \text{state_digest_bytes} \quad (\text{raw nonce, not hashed})$$

- **TPM 2.0:** Extract `qualifyingData`. Verify:

$$\text{qualifyingData} = \text{sha256}(\text{nonce_bytes} \parallel \text{state_digest_bytes})$$

- (c) Verify the platform attestation evidence signature using the platform vendor’s certificate chain (e.g., AMD ARK/ASK, Intel SGX/TDX quoting enclave CA, AWS Nitro CA). Reject on any binding or signature failure.

Step 10. Verify platform_report and image measurement.

Verify that `R.platform_report.image_digest` matches a reproducible-build allow-list entry (if `R.platform_report.allowlist_ref` is present, fetch and validate against it). If `R.attestation_mode = “periodic”`, verify `R.platform_report.cadence_ms ≤ R.attestation_policy.ta`. Reject on allow-list miss or cadence violation.

Step 11. Check policy_state_digest against expected policy.

Verify `R.policy_state_digest = expected_policy_digest`. The `expected_policy_digest` is the value issued by the control plane (Policy Engine / Session Orchestrator) for this session. Reject on mismatch. This confirms the UMCEE enforced the intended egress allowlist, write-blocking rules, TTL, model/route profile, and DP budget thresholds.

Step 12. Verify terminal attestation commitments (proof-of-zero).

In the terminal entry `A[n-1]` (where `kind = “stop”`), verify the state claims commit to:

- `R.zeroization_report_digest`—confirming the teardown zeroization procedure and scope.
- `R.teardown_digest`—confirming teardown/finalization.
- If `R.decision = “RELEASE”`: `R.response_ciphertext_digest` is present and committed. If `R.decision = “WITHHOLD”`: this field **MUST** be absent.
- If `R.dp_tuple.enabled = true`: `R.update_digest` is present and committed (the `H(U) safeguard`—i.e., the hash of the update artifact is bound into the terminal `state_digest`, preventing post-attestation payload substitution).

Step 13. Verify attestation bundle digest cross-check (if applicable).

If `R.attestation_bundle_digest` is present (required for compact profile; optional cross-check for full profile): construct the canonical three-key bundle object

$$\{ \text{“attestations”}: [\dots], \text{“certs”}: [\dots], \text{“key_material_by_kid”}: \{ \dots \} \}$$

canonicalize via JCS, hash, and verify the result matches `R.attestation_bundle_digest`. Reject on mismatch (split-world prevention).

Step 14. DP tuple verification (conditional: `dp_tuple.enabled = true`).

If `R.dp_tuple.enabled = false` (inference-only mode), skip to Step 15. Otherwise:

- (a) **Recompute tuple_digest.** Construct a copy of `R.dp_tuple` excluding the `tuple_digest` field itself. Canonicalize via JCS, encode to UTF-8 bytes, and compute:

$$\text{sha256}(\text{JCS}(\text{dp_tuple_sans_digest}))$$

Verify it matches `R.dp_tuple(tuple_digest)`. Reject on mismatch.

- (b) **Verify mechanism–guarantee consistency.** Enforce the required mappings:

$$\text{"laplace"} \implies \text{guarantee.type} = \text{"pure_dp"}, \text{guarantee.delta} = \text{"0"}$$

$$\text{"gaussian"} \implies \text{guarantee.type} = \text{"approx_dp"}$$

$$\text{"zcdp_gaussian"} \implies \text{guarantee.type} = \text{"zcdp"}$$

$$\text{"rdp_subsampling_gaussian"} \implies \text{guarantee.type} = \text{"rdp"}$$

Reject on inconsistency.

- (c) **Verify decimal encoding.** Confirm all `string(decimal)` fields in `dp_tuple` conform to the canonical pattern `^(0|[1-9][0-9]*)(\.[0-9]*[1-9])?$` with no exponent notation, no leading `+`, and no leading zeros. Verify domain constraints: $C > 0$, $S > 0$, $\sigma > 0$ (or $b > 0$), $\varepsilon > 0$, etc. Reject on any syntactic or domain violation.
- (d) **Verify calibration rule conformance.** Dispatch on `R.dp_tuple.calibration.rule`:
- `"dwork_roth_1p25"` (Gaussian) [52]: verify

$$\sigma \geq \frac{S \sqrt{2 \ln(1.25/\delta)}}{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

- `"laplace_scale"` (Laplace): verify $b \geq S/\varepsilon$ and `guarantee.delta = "0"`.
- `"zcdp_rho"` (zCDP): verify consistency via $\varepsilon(\delta) = \rho + 2\sqrt{\rho \ln(1/\delta)}$.
- `"rdp_subsampling_gaussian_v1"` (RDP): verify accountant fields (`sample_rate`, `rounds`) and, if `rdp_curve` is present, check consistency with `noise_multiplier` under the declared rule.

Reject on calibration failure.

- (e) **Verify sensitivity derivation** (if `sensitivity.source = "derived_from_clip"`). Apply the derivation function registered for the active `calibration.rule` and `adjacency`:

$$S = \begin{cases} C & \text{if adjacency} = \text{"add_remove"} \\ 2C & \text{if adjacency} = \text{"replace_one"} \end{cases}$$

Reject if `R.dp_tuple.sensitivity.bound` does not match the derived value.

- (f) **Verify tuple_digest is committed in terminal state claims.** Confirm that the terminal attestation entry's `state_digest` was computed over state claims that include `R.dp_tuple(tuple_digest)`. (This prevents swapping Γ across sessions.)

Step 15. Aggregator-side privacy budget enforcement (conditional: learning enabled).

If the verifier is acting as the secure aggregator and learning is enabled (we write \hat{U} for the transmitted update artifact, denoted $\hat{\Delta}$ in the architecture description):

- (a) **Recompute** $H(\hat{U})$. Receive the update artifact payload \hat{U} . Compute:

$$update_digest_recomputed = sha256(CBOR_{preferred}(update_container))$$

per the Update Encoding specification. Verify $update_digest_recomputed = R.update_digest$. Reject on mismatch (prevents payload tampering post-attestation).

- (b) **Enforce cumulative privacy budget**. Using the attested DP tuple Γ and the aggregator's *privacy_budget_state*, compute the cumulative ε_{total} (via moments accountant, Rényi accountant, or simple composition as appropriate). Reject \hat{U} if the policy budget threshold would be exceeded.
- (c) **Admit or reject**. On acceptance: merge \hat{U} into the global model; discard \hat{U} ; zeroize transient buffers within the purge window; persist only an acceptance receipt binding $\{session_id, attestation_chain_root, H(\hat{U})\}$ to the transparency log. On rejection: discard \hat{U} ; optionally blacklist the image measurement until re-attested; notify the verifier.

Step 16. Transcript commitment verification (optional, by regulated client).

If the regulated client can derive the commitment key K (e.g., from a TLS exporter):

- If $R.transcript_commitment.scheme = "hmac-sha256"$: derive K via $R.transcript_commitment.k$; recompute $HMAC-SHA-256(K, transcript_bytes)$, and verify it matches $R.transcript_commitment$.
- If $R.transcript_commitment.scheme = "salted-sha256"$: decode $R.transcript_commitment.salt$ to $salt_bytes$, recompute $SHA-256(salt_bytes \parallel transcript_bytes)$, and verify match.

Reject on mismatch (indicates transcript tampering or substitution).

Return ACCEPT if all applicable steps pass.

6.2 Verification Modes

Not all steps apply to every deployment. Table 3 summarizes which steps are required under each operational mode.

6.3 Implementation Notes

Ordering sensitivity. Steps 1–4 establish receipt-level integrity and must precede chain-level checks. Steps 5–8 establish chain integrity and must precede per-entry evidence verification (Step 9). DP tuple verification (Step 14) depends on chain validity (Steps 5–8) because `tuple_digest` is committed via `state_digest` in the terminal attestation; verifying calibration before confirming the chain is unbroken could allow a forged chain to carry a seemingly valid DP tuple.

Memory budget. Step 8 requires buffering the full attestation chain. At the recommended `maxItems` limit of 10,000 entries and ≈ 75 bytes per `state_digest` string, the JCS array input is ≈ 750 KB. For a representative periodic-mode session at $\tau = 500$ ms running for 30 minutes ($\approx 3,600$ entries) it is ≈ 270 KB. Verifiers should pre-allocate accordingly and reject receipts exceeding configured chain-length limits before attempting the hash.

Table 3: Step applicability by operational mode. ✓ = required; “—” = skip.

Step	Inference-only (<code>dp_tuple.enabled</code> = <code>false</code>)	Learning-enabled (<code>dp_tuple.enabled</code> = <code>true</code>)	Start/stop attestation	Periodic attestation
1–4 (parse, nonce, digest, sig)	✓	✓	✓	✓
5 (chain bookending)	✓	✓	exactly 2 entries	✓
6 (freshness counter)	✓	✓	gap unconstrained	no-gap
7 (signature policy)	✓	✓	✓	✓
8 (<code>attestation_chain_root</code>)	✓	✓	✓	✓
9 (platform evidence binding)	✓	✓	✓	✓
10 (image measurement)	✓	✓	✓	✓ + cadence
11 (<code>policy_state_digest</code>)	✓	✓	✓	✓
12 (terminal commitments)	✓ (no <code>update_digest</code>)	✓	✓	✓
13 (bundle digest)	profile-dep.	profile-dep.	profile-dep.	profile-dep.
14 (DP tuple)	—	✓	✓	✓
15 (aggregator budget)	—	✓ (agg. only)	✓	✓
16 (transcript commitment)	optional	optional	optional	optional

Interoperability. Implementers reconstructing this procedure from the field-level constraints in Table 2 alone risk omitting cross-field checks (e.g., the `mech↔guarantee.type` consistency check in Step 14b, or the sensitivity derivation in Step 14e). This algorithm is normative: a conformant EPR-1.1 verifier **MUST** implement all applicable steps in the specified order.

7 Toward Provider-Integrated Trust Boundary Extension

The boundary-edge deployment described in Section 3.4.4 reflects the practical reality for most regulated organizations today: inference is consumed through a managed API, and the UMCEE provides attested, cryptographically evidenced non-persistence for everything within its control—prompt minimization, post-processing, egress gating, attestation, and teardown—while the inference step itself is governed by the provider’s contractual commitments. This configuration already represents a substantial improvement over the status quo, in which no component of the pipeline produces verifiable non-persistence evidence. Nevertheless, the inference call remains the one segment of the data path where the compliance posture rests on organizational trust rather than cryptographic proof.

The architecture was designed to close this gap. As noted in Section 3.4.4, the attestation chain’s support for multiple `component` labels and the receipt schema’s capacity to incorporate attestation entries from distinct enclaves within a single session provide the structural foundation for extending the trust boundary to include the model execution endpoint—without any modification to the EPR-1.1 receipt schema or the verification protocol specified in Section 6. This section develops that observation into a concrete integration proposal and examines its practical constraints.

7.1 Integration Architecture

A cloud provider offering LLM inference could deploy its model-serving infrastructure inside a TEE (e.g., an AMD SEV-SNP confidential VM, an Intel TDX trust domain, or an AWS Nitro Enclave) and expose the same managed API surface that customers already consume, while additionally emitting attestation entries that the customer’s UMCEE incorporates into the session’s attestation chain.

From the customer’s UMCEE. The interaction is minimally modified. The UMCEE sends the minimized, tokenized prompt to the provider endpoint over a mutually authenticated channel, as in the boundary-edge configuration. The provider’s inference enclave returns both the inference result and one or more signed attestation entries produced under its own hardware root of trust. The UMCEE validates the provider’s attestation entry signatures against the provider’s published trust anchors, verifies that the entry binds the session’s freshness nonce (`freshness.nonce`) and a state digest covering the provider’s attested policy configuration, and appends the entry to the session’s attestation chain under a distinct `component` label (e.g., `"inference-enclave-provider"`). The augmented chain then flows to the Egress Gate and into the receipt as in the standard pipeline.

From the provider’s inference enclave. The provider’s enclave is measured at instantiation; its `image_digest` is published or registered in an allow-list that the customer’s verifier can check. At inference time, the enclave constructs a `state_claims` object that commits to its own `platform_report.image_digest`, the session’s `freshness.nonce`, its local policy configuration (e.g., no logging, no persistence of prompt or key-value cache, memory confinement mode), and—critically—the same `policy_state_digest` issued by the customer’s Session Orchestrator, binding the provider’s attestation to the customer’s session policy. The enclave signs the resulting `state_digest` using a key rooted in its platform’s hardware attestation mechanism and returns the signed entry alongside the inference response.

From the verifier’s perspective. The receipt’s attestation chain now contains entries from both the customer’s UMCEE (with `component="leaf"` or equivalent) and the provider’s inference enclave (with a distinct `component` value). The `attestation_chain_root` is computed over the full ordered chain, covering both sets of entries. The verification protocol (Section 6.1) processes the provider’s entries using the same steps—signature verification (Step 7), platform evidence binding (Step 9), image measurement validation (Step 10)—with the provider’s trust anchors resolved via the certificate material in the receipt. No new verification steps are required; the existing algorithm handles multi-component chains by design.

7.2 Provider Incentives

The proposal is framed not as a compliance burden imposed on providers but as a commercially motivated service-tier extension. In regulated markets—healthcare, financial services, legal, and government—the ability to offer cryptographically verifiable non-persistence as a managed service option constitutes a competitive differentiator. Every major LLM cloud provider already offers contractual non-retention commitments (Section 2, “Policy-based non-retention promises”); the limitation, as this report has argued, is that these commitments are not independently verifiable on a per-session basis. A provider that supplements its contractual promise with per-session attestation entries convertible into EPR-1.1 receipts offers its regulated customers something no competitor provides: cryptographic evidence, not just contractual assurance.

For providers already investing in confidential computing infrastructure—and several major cloud platforms have made substantial commitments to TEE-based inference offerings—adding attestation-entry emission to the inference pipeline is an incremental integration. The provider’s existing TEE instantiation, measurement, and key-management infrastructure supplies the attestation primitive; the additional requirement is to construct a `state_claims` object per the schema defined in Appendix B, sign it, and return the signed entry alongside the inference response. The computational overhead of one additional SHA-256 hash and one ECDSA signature per inference call is negligible relative to the cost of model inference itself.

7.3 Current Practical Constraints

Intellectual honesty requires acknowledging that TEE-hosted inference for frontier-scale language models involves engineering challenges that are not yet fully resolved at industry scale.

GPU TEE maturity. Large language model inference is overwhelmingly GPU-bound. GPU-level confidential computing support—notably NVIDIA’s confidential computing mode on H100 and H200 accelerators—is available but not yet widely deployed for production inference workloads at the scale of frontier models. Memory capacity constraints in certain TEE configurations may further limit the model sizes that can be served within a single enclave. These are active areas of hardware and systems development; the trajectory is toward broader support, but the current deployment footprint is limited.

Proprietary model weights and code transparency. A provider deploying inference inside an attested enclave may treat both its model weights and its inference code as proprietary. In this case, the customer’s verifier can confirm—via the platform attestation evidence and the published `image_digest`—that a specific, measured code image executed inside a memory-confined TEE with attested non-persistence policy, but cannot independently audit what that code does with the prompt beyond what the attestation claims. The attestation proves *that* a specific binary ran in a non-persisting environment; it does not prove *what* that binary does internally absent code transparency.

This constitutes a meaningful trust reduction compared to the boundary-edge deployment: the customer trusts the TEE hardware root of trust and the code measurement rather than the provider’s organizational controls and contractual remedies. The compliance posture shifts from “trust the provider’s policy” to “trust the provider’s measured code identity and the hardware attestation that it ran in a non-persisting enclave.” This is a materially stronger assurance—the attack surface is reduced from organizational process failures to hardware root-of-trust compromise—but it is not zero trust. Full transparency would require the provider to publish its inference code for independent review or to submit to third-party code audits whose results are bound into the attestation, either of which is in tension with model IP protection. This is an inherent trade-off between verifiability and intellectual property, not a flaw in the architecture; the architecture supports the strongest guarantee the provider is willing to offer, and the receipt records exactly which guarantee was provided.

7.4 Progressive Assurance and Deployment Trajectory

The architecture’s extensibility means that regulated organizations can progressively strengthen their compliance posture as the confidential computing ecosystem matures, without changing the receipt schema, the verification protocol, or the verifier implementation:

1. **Boundary-edge deployment (available today).** The UMCEE provides attested non-persistence for all processing it controls; inference is covered by the provider’s contractual commitments. The receipt records this configuration via `policy_state_digest` and the absence of provider-side attestation entries.
2. **Extended-boundary deployment with attested provider enclave.** The provider deploys inference inside a TEE and contributes attestation entries to the session chain. The receipt provides end-to-end attestation coverage. The customer trusts the provider’s code measurement and the hardware root of trust.

3. **Extended-boundary deployment with audited or open-source inference code.** The provider publishes or submits to independent audit its inference code, enabling the customer’s verifier to confirm that the measured `image_digest` corresponds to code that faithfully performs inference without logging, caching, or persisting inputs. This configuration provides the strongest available guarantee within the TEE trust model.

At every level, the EPR-1.1 receipt records which configuration was active for the session, giving auditors a clear, per-session view of the assurance level achieved. An organization operating under boundary-edge deployment today can migrate to extended-boundary deployment when its provider offers TEE-hosted inference—and the receipts from both periods remain independently verifiable under the same schema and verification protocol, preserving audit continuity across the transition.

8 Conclusion

This report specified an architecture for running LLM workloads on regulated data with auditable non-persistence guarantees within an explicitly defined trust boundary. The core contributions are:

1. The Universal Memory-Confined Execution Environment (UMCEE), which enforces non-persistence through layered runtime mechanisms—system-call and hypervisor-exit interception, DMA isolation via IOMMU policy, sub-swap-interval shredding with per-session encryption, and hardware-assisted zeroization at teardown.
2. The Epheia Privacy Receipt 1.1 (EPR-1.1), a receipt schema that binds session identity, attestation chain integrity, policy configuration, egress decisions, proof-of-zero termination, and (when learning is enabled) differential-privacy parameters and update artifact hashes into a single signed, independently verifiable artifact.
3. A normative 16-step verification protocol that specifies the order and cross-field dependencies required for conformant receipt verification, together with mode-specific applicability rules for inference-only, learning-enabled, periodic, and start/stop configurations.
4. A threat model and trust-boundary framework that makes explicit what the architecture defends against, what it assumes, and what residual risks remain—including the model-endpoint interface and the progressive trust-boundary extension pathway developed in Section 7.

This document is an architecture specification. A reference implementation—comprising a UMCEE prototype on AMD SEV-SNP, a conformant EPR-1.1 receipt issuer and verifier, and integration with a managed LLM inference endpoint—is planned as subsequent work. Empirical evaluation targets include attestation-chain emission overhead, shred-scheduler latency under representative workloads, verification throughput as a function of chain length, and trusted computing base (TCB) measurement for the UMCEE image.

Several directions for future work are noted throughout the report and collected here for reference. The flat attestation-chain commitment imposes verification cost linear in chain length; a future EPR version may introduce a Merkle-chain construction to enable incremental verification and sublinear proof sizes. The cryptographic primitives used in EPR-1.1 (ECDSA, SHA-256) are not post-quantum secure; migration to post-quantum signature schemes (e.g., ML-DSA/Dilithium) is accommodated by the schema’s algorithm-qualified fields but is not yet specified. Traffic-analysis side channels on encrypted UMCEE-to-endpoint communication are acknowledged but not mitigated by the current design. Finally, all normative schemas and encoding conventions required

for independent review and implementation are specified in the appendices of this report (see Appendix D for additional specifications and Appendices B and C for full schemas); future companion documents may expand on implementation guidance and platform-specific errata.

The gap between contractual non-retention promises and cryptographically verifiable non-persistence proofs is real and consequential for regulated AI adoption. This architecture provides the enforcement mechanisms, the evidentiary chain, and the receipt artifact to begin closing that gap—moving regulated AI compliance from a trust-based posture to an evidence-based one.

Disclosure

The author is affiliated with a company developing related technology and may have a financial interest in this work. The author has filed provisional patent applications related to aspects of the techniques described.

Acknowledgments

The author is solely responsible for all architectural decisions, technical claims, and normative content. AI-assisted tools were used during manuscript preparation.

License

© 2026 Vincent P. Giacomo / Epheia, Inc. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

References

- [1] J. Vrdoljak, Z. Boban, M. Vilović, M. Kumrić, and J. Božić, “A Review of Large Language Models in Medical Education, Clinical Decision Support, and Healthcare Administration,” *Healthcare*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 603, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.3390/healthcare13060603.
- [2] A. Goyal, J. P. Pendyala, and R. Bhat, “Towards an AI Framework for Scalable Compliance Monitoring in Regulated Sectors,” in *2025 IEEE International Conference on Compute, Control, Network & Photonics (ICCCNP)*, Bangalore, India: IEEE, Sep. 2025, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/ICCCNP63914.2025.11233371.
- [3] S. Hassani, M. Sabetzadeh, D. Amyot, and J. Liao, “Rethinking Legal Compliance Automation: Opportunities with Large Language Models,” in *2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, Reykjavik, Iceland: IEEE, Jun. 2024, pp. 432–440. doi: 10.1109/RE59067.2024.00051.
- [4] K. Navaie, “From rights to runtime: Privacy engineering for agentic AI,” *AI Magazine*, vol. 46, no. 4, p. e70036, Dec. 2025, doi: 10.1002/aaai.70036.
- [5] Z. Chkirbene, R. Hamila, A. Gouisssem, and U. Devrim, “Large Language Models (LLM) in Industry: A Survey of Applications, Challenges, and Trends,” in *2024 IEEE 21st International Conference on Smart Communities: Improving Quality of Life using*

- AI, Robotics and IoT (HONET)*, Doha, Qatar: IEEE, Dec. 2024, pp. 229–234. doi: 10.1109/HONET63146.2024.10822885.
- [6] Y. Liu *et al.*, “How Privacy-Savvy Are Large Language Models? A Case Study on Compliance and Privacy Technical Review,” 2024, arXiv. doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2409.02375.
- [7] J. Jain, N. Dhanasekaran, and M. T. Diab, “From Complexity to Clarity: AI/NLP’s Role in Regulatory Compliance,” in *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2025*, Vienna, Austria: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2025, pp. 26629–26641. doi: 10.18653/v1/2025.findings-acl.1366.
- [8] C. Meijer and B. Van Gastel, “Self-Encrypting Deception: Weaknesses in the Encryption of Solid State Drives,” in *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, San Francisco, CA, USA: IEEE, May 2019, pp. 72–87. doi: 10.1109/SP.2019.00088.
- [9] C. Li, I. Gim, and L. Zhong, “Confidential Prompting: Privacy-preserving LLM Inference on Cloud,” 2024, arXiv. doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2409.19134.
- [10] N. Panwar, S. Sharma, P. Gupta, D. Ghosh, S. Mehrotra, and N. Venkatasubramanian, “IoT Expunge: Implementing Verifiable Retention of IoT Data,” in *Proceedings of the 10th ACM Conference on Data and Application Security and Privacy (CODASPY ’20)*, New Orleans, LA, USA: ACM, Mar. 2020, pp. 283–294. doi: 10.1145/3374664.3375737.
- [11] K. Onarlioglu, C. Mulliner, W. Robertson, and E. Kirda, “PrivExec: Private Execution as an Operating System Service,” in *2013 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, Berkeley, CA: IEEE, May 2013, pp. 206–220. doi: 10.1109/SP.2013.24.
- [12] J. Lyle, S. Mead, and K. Rider, “Disk Drive I/O Commands and Write Blocking,” in *Advances in Digital Forensics III* (IFIP, vol. 242), P. Craiger and S. Sheno, Eds. New York, NY: Springer, 2007, pp. 163–177. doi: 10.1007/978-0-387-73742-3_11.
- [13] P. Tobin, N.-A. Le-Khac, and M.-T. Kechadi, “A lightweight software write-blocker for virtual machine forensics,” in *2016 Sixth International Conference on Innovative Computing Technology (INTECH)*, Dublin, Ireland: IEEE, Aug. 2016, pp. 730–735. doi: 10.1109/INTECH.2016.7845141.
- [14] M. Roffel and X. Lin, “Write Blocker for Internet of Things Flash Technologies,” in *2023 20th Annual International Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST)*, Copenhagen, Denmark: IEEE, Aug. 2023, pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1109/PST58708.2023.10320158.
- [15] Intel Corporation, “Intel[®] Trust Domain Extensions,” White Paper, doc. 343961-003US, Jun. 2025.
- [16] Amazon Web Services, Inc., “AWS Nitro Enclaves: User Guide,” 2026. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [17] L. Dewey and D. Gonzalez Villalobos, “SEV-SNP Platform Attestation Using VirTEE/SEV,” Advanced Micro Devices, Inc., Publication no. 58217, Rev. 1.2, Jul. 2023.
- [18] H. Birkholz, D. Thaler, M. Richardson, N. Smith, and W. Pan, “Remote ATtestation procedureS (RATS) Architecture,” RFC Editor, RFC9334, Jan. 2023. doi: 10.17487/RFC9334.

- [19] C. Dwork, F. McSherry, K. Nissim, and A. Smith, “Calibrating Noise to Sensitivity in Private Data Analysis,” in *Theory of Cryptography (TCC 2006)*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 3876, S. Halevi and T. Rabin, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2006, pp. 265–284. doi: 10.1007/11681878_14.
- [20] H. Liang, W. Zhang, X. He, K. Wu, and H. Xing, “An Improved Privacy and Utility Analysis of Differentially Private SGD with Bounded Domain and Smooth Losses,” 2025, arXiv. doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2502.17772.
- [21] P. Satheesh Kumar and Saravanan M., “System and method for statistical federated learning,” U.S. Patent Appl. Publ. US20240378457A1, Nov. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.justia.com/patent/20240378457>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [22] R. Xu, N. B. Angel, Y. Zhou, A. Anwar, and H. H. Ludwig, “Privacy-preserving federated learning,” US12160504B2, Dec. 03, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US12160504B2/en>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [23] H. B. McMahan, D. M. Bacon, J. Konečný, and X. Yu, “Communication efficient federated learning,” EP3660754A1, Jun. 03, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/EP3660754A1/en>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [24] K. Bonawitz *et al.*, “Practical Secure Aggregation for Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning,” in *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, Dallas, TX, USA: ACM, Oct. 2017, pp. 1175–1191. doi: 10.1145/3133956.3133982.
- [25] A. P. P. Hartono, A. Brito, and C. Fetzer, “CRISP: Confidentiality, Rollback, and Integrity Storage Protection for Confidential Cloud-Native Computing,” in *2024 IEEE 17th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*, Shenzhen, China: IEEE, Jul. 2024, pp. 141–152. doi: 10.1109/CLOUD62652.2024.00026.
- [26] X. Luo and Y. Zhang, “QuickStorage: A Write-optimized Efficient Storage System for Trusted Execution Environments,” in *Proceedings of the 2023 4th International Conference on Computing, Networks and Internet of Things*, Xiamen, China: ACM, May 2023, pp. 145–150. doi: 10.1145/3603781.3603806.
- [27] B. Laurie, E. Messeri, and R. Stradling, “Certificate Transparency Version 2.0,” RFC Editor, RFC9162, Dec. 2021. doi: 10.17487/RFC9162.
- [28] “Enterprise privacy at OpenAI.” [Online]. Available: <https://openai.com/enterprise-privacy/>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [29] “OpenAI Data Processing Addendum.” [Online]. Available: <https://openai.com/policies/data-processing-addendum/>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [30] “Business data privacy, security, and compliance.” [Online]. Available: <https://openai.com/business-data/>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [31] “Custom data retention controls for Enterprise plans,” Anthropic Privacy Center. [Online]. Available: <https://privacy.claude.com/en/articles/10440198-custom-data-retention-controls-for-enterprise-plans>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.

- [32] “Security, privacy, and responsible AI – Amazon Bedrock – AWS,” Amazon Web Services, Inc. [Online]. Available: <https://aws.amazon.com/bedrock/security-privacy-responsible-ai/>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [33] “Vertex AI and zero data retention,” Generative AI on Vertex AI, Google Cloud Documentation. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/generative-ai/docs/vertex-ai-zero-data-retention>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [34] “Protection of customer data in Azure.” [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/security/fundamentals/protection-customer-data>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [35] “Privacy & Security,” Perplexity. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.perplexity.ai/docs/resources/privacy-security>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [36] “Terms of Service – Enterprise,” xAI. [Online]. Available: <https://x.ai/legal/terms-of-service-enterprise>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [37] D. N. Jaidan, M. Carrere, Z. Chemli, and R. Poisvert, “Data Anonymization for Privacy Aware Machine Learning,” in *Machine Learning, Optimization, and Data Science* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 11943), G. Nicosia, P. Pardalos, R. Umeton, G. Giuffrida, and V. Sciacca, Eds. Cham: Springer, 2019, pp. 725–737. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-37599-7_60.
- [38] M. Vardalachakis and C. Kalloniatis, “The role of Anonymization Techniques in Differential Privacy,” in *2025 International Conference on Computer Technology Applications (ICCTA)*, Vienna, Austria: IEEE, May 2025, pp. 14–18. doi: 10.1109/ICCTA65425.2025.11166256.
- [39] H. Fereidooni *et al.*, “SAFELearn: Secure Aggregation for private FEderated Learning,” in *2021 IEEE Security and Privacy Workshops (SPW)*, San Francisco, CA, USA: IEEE, May 2021, pp. 56–62. doi: 10.1109/SPW53761.2021.00017.
- [40] H. Us Sami and B. Güler, “Secure Gradient Aggregation With Sparsification for Resource-Limited Federated Learning,” *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 72, no. 11, pp. 6883–6899, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2024.3403475.
- [41] H. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. Agüera y Arcas, “Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data,” in *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics (AISTATS)*, Fort Lauderdale, FL, USA, Apr. 2017, pp. 1273–1282. arXiv: 1602.05629.
- [42] S. Cosman *et al.*, “User behavior model development with private federated learning,” US20210192078A1, Jun. 24, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20210192078A1/en>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [43] A. Fireberger, H. Bitran, S. Admati, T. Baumel, and D. Karmon, “System and Method for Federated Learning,” US20240211633A1, Jun. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20240211633A1/en>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.
- [44] D. Ying, L. Ruan, J. Han, Q. Li, and G. Wu, “Federated learning in O-RAN,” US20220012645A1, Jan. 13, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20220012645A1/en>. Accessed: Feb. 20, 2026.

- [45] M. S. Alvim, M. E. Andrés, K. Chatzikokolakis, P. Degano, and C. Palamidessi, “On the information leakage of differentially-private mechanisms,” *Journal of Computer Security*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 427–469, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.3233/JCS-150528.
- [46] L. Zhu, Z. Liu, and S. Han, “Deep Leakage from Gradients,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32 (NeurIPS 2019)*, Vancouver, Canada, 2019, pp. 14774–14784. arXiv: 1906.08935.
- [47] J. C. Zhao, A. Sharma, A. R. Elkordy, Y. H. Ezzeldin, S. Avestimehr, and S. Bagchi, “LOKI: Large-scale Data Reconstruction Attack against Federated Learning through Model Manipulation,” 2023, arXiv. doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2303.12233.
- [48] A. Caulfield, A. J. Neto, N. Rattanaivanon, and I. De Oliveira Nunes, “TRACES: TEE-based Runtime Auditing for Commodity Embedded Systems,” in *2024 Annual Computer Security Applications Conference (ACSAC)*, Honolulu, HI, USA: IEEE, Dec. 2024, pp. 257–270. doi: 10.1109/ACSAC63791.2024.00035.
- [49] M. S. M. S. Annamalai and E. De Cristofaro, “Nearly Tight Black-Box Auditing of Differentially Private Machine Learning,” 2024, arXiv. doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2405.14106.
- [50] R. Shokri, M. Stronati, C. Song, and V. Shmatikov, “Membership Inference Attacks Against Machine Learning Models,” in *2017 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, San Jose, CA, USA: IEEE, May 2017, pp. 3–18. doi: 10.1109/SP.2017.41.
- [51] J. Van Bulck *et al.*, “Foreshadow: Extracting the Keys to the Intel SGX Kingdom with Transient Out-of-Order Execution,” in *27th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 18)*, Baltimore, MD, USA: USENIX Association, Aug. 2018, pp. 991–1008.
- [52] C. Dwork and A. Roth, “The Algorithmic Foundations of Differential Privacy,” *Foundations and Trends in Theoretical Computer Science*, vol. 9, no. 3–4, pp. 211–407, 2014. doi: 10.1561/04000000042.

A EPR-1.1 Receipt Fields — Full Normative Detail

This appendix provides the complete normative field-level specification for the EPR-1.1 privacy receipt schema, including encoding patterns, DoS-prevention size limits, domain-separation conventions, and per-platform evidence binding profiles. Table 2 in the main body provides a condensed summary; this table is the authoritative reference for implementers and verifiers.

Table 4: EPR-1.1 receipt fields — full normative detail (paths, types, requiredness, semantics, encoding constraints, and DoS-prevention recommendations). Req.: Y = required; O = optional; C = conditional (required if predicate holds).

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
Receipt identity, freshness, tamper-evidence version	string	Y	Receipt version identifier. Must equal "EPR-1.1".

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
receipt_profile	string	Y	Receipt packaging profile. Enum: "EPR-1.1-compact" (compact receipt; attestations and certificate material (<code>certs</code> , <code>key_material_by_kid</code>) MAY be omitted and provided out-of-band; <code>attestation_bundle_digest</code> REQUIRED when omitted) or "EPR-1.1-full" (full receipt includes attestations and certificate material (<code>certs</code> , <code>key_material_by_kid</code>)).
receipt_id	string	Y	Globally unique receipt identifier (recommended: UUIDv7 or 128-bit random base64url). Non-empty; max 128 chars.
issued_at	string (date-time)	Y	Receipt issuance time in RFC 3339 / ISO 8601 (format: <code>date-time</code>). MUST be covered by <code>receipt_digest</code> .
session_id	string	Y	Unique identifier for the attested session (e.g., <code>sess_XXXXXXXX</code>). Suggested pattern: <code>~sess_[A-Za-z0-9_-]+</code> .
action	string	Y	Action label for the attested run (e.g., "chat"). Non-empty string; max 64 chars recommended.
freshness.nonce	string	Y	Verifier/client challenge to prevent replay. MUST be at least 16 bytes (128 bits) of CSPRNG output; SHOULD be 32 bytes (256 bits). Encoded as RFC 4648 base64url without padding. MUST be covered by <code>receipt_digest</code> and cryptographically bound into each platform attestation evidence blob. See normative details below.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
<p>freshness.nonce — normative requirements. Implementations MUST NOT use deterministic or predictable nonce generation (e.g., counters, timestamps, or non-cryptographic PRNGs). Verifiers MUST reject receipts where the decoded nonce is fewer than 16 bytes. Implementations SHOULD enforce a maximum decoded nonce length of 64 bytes to prevent DoS via oversized nonces in evidence binding (particularly relevant for platforms with fixed-size report-data fields). Verifier MUST decode to <code>nonce.bytes</code>; cryptographic operations on the nonce (e.g., <code>sha256(...)</code>) MUST be applied to <code>nonce.bytes</code> (not the base64 text). The binding convention is determined by the <code>evidence.format</code> value of each attestation entry; compliant verifiers MUST implement the corresponding platform-specific binding profile as specified in Appendix D. <i>Normative per-platform conventions:</i> AMD SEV-SNP (<code>"amd-sev-snp-report"</code>): 64-byte <code>REPORT_DATA = sha256(nonce.bytes) state.digest.bytes (32 + 32 bytes)</code>. Intel TDX (<code>"intel-tdx-quote"</code>): 64-byte <code>REPORTDATA = sha256(nonce.bytes) state.digest.bytes (32 + 32 bytes)</code>. AWS Nitro (<code>"aws-nitro-doc"</code>): variable-length <code>user_data = nonce.bytes state.digest.bytes</code> (raw nonce, not hashed). TPM 2.0 (<code>"tpm2-quote"</code>): <code>qualifyingData = sha256(nonce.bytes state.digest.bytes)</code>.</p>			
<code>receipt_digest</code>	string	Y	<p>Digest over the receipt JSON value after removing fields <code>receipt_digest</code> and <code>receipt_signature</code>. All other fields, including <code>receipt_kid</code> if present, are included in the digest input. Recommended: RFC 8785 JCS canonicalization → UTF-8 bytes → hash. Value is algorithm-qualified: <code><hash-alg>:<digest-hex></code>, where <code><digest-hex></code> is exactly 64 lowercase hexadecimal characters; therefore <code><hash-alg></code> MUST denote a 256-bit hash (e.g., <code>sha-256</code>, <code>sha3-256</code>). A verifier recomputes this digest and rejects the receipt on mismatch. Suggested pattern: <code>^[a-z0-9-]+:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code>.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
receipt_signature	string	Y	Digital signature over a domain-separated signing input derived from <code>receipt_digest</code> . Define <code>sig_input = UTF8("EPR-1.1/receipt_digest/") UTF8(receipt_digest)</code> , where both strings are encoded as UTF-8 bytes and concatenated; the signature MUST be computed over <code>sig_input</code> . The domain-separation prefix is version-locked: future EPR versions (e.g., EPR-1.2) MUST use their own version-qualified prefix; implementations MUST NOT strip or rewrite domain separators during version negotiation or migration to prevent cross-version signature confusion. Recommended profiles: <code>ecdsa-p256-sha256</code> (ECDSA P-256 with SHA-256) or <code>ecdsa-p384-sha384</code> (ECDSA P-384 with SHA-384). Example encoding: <code>ecdsa-p384-sha384:<b64url(der-sig)></code> , where <code><b64url(der-sig)></code> is a DER-encoded ECDSA signature (bytes) base64url-encoded (RFC 4648, no padding). Suggested pattern: <code>^(ecdsa-p256-sha256 ecdsa-p384-sha384):[A-Za-z0-9_-]+\$</code> . Implementations SHOULD enforce a maximum encoded signature length (e.g., ≤ 512 chars) to prevent DoS.
receipt_kid	string	O	Key identifier for <code>receipt_signature</code> (useful when multiple signing keys are possible). Non-empty string. Note: <code>receipt_kid</code> , when present, is included in the <code>receipt_digest</code> computation (only <code>receipt_digest</code> and <code>receipt_signature</code> are excluded), so an attacker cannot swap the key identifier without invalidating the digest.
Egress decision + output binding (Egress Gate)			
decision	string	Y	Egress Gate decision. Enum: "RELEASE" or "WITHHOLD". MUST be covered by <code>receipt_digest</code> .

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
response_ciphertext_digest	string	C	<p>Required iff <code>decision="RELEASE"</code>. Commitment to the exact ciphertext bytes released to the regulated client. MUST be SHA-256 over the raw ciphertext bytes (not over a base64 text form unless that is explicitly defined as the canonical bytes). Committing to the ciphertext (rather than the plaintext) binds the Egress Gate's RELEASE decision to the exact encrypted payload without requiring the Gate to see or retain plaintext, preserving the receipts-only property. Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code>. Pattern: <code>^sha256:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code>. Architecture note: the Egress Gate's signing scope binds <code>H(response_ciphertext)</code> into the receipt <i>only</i> when <code>decision="RELEASE"</code>; when <code>decision="WITHHOLD"</code>, the Gate MUST omit this field from both the receipt and the terminal <code>state_claims</code> (i.e., the binding is conditional on RELEASE, not unconditional).</p>

Attestation chain (monotonic freshness, cadence τ , dual signatures)

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
signature_policy	string	Y	<p>Attestation signature cardinality policy. Enum: "dual" or "single". MUST be "dual" unless the deployment profile explicitly documents a single-signer threat model. MUST be covered by <code>receipt_digest</code>, making the policy tamper-evident—an attacker cannot downgrade from "dual" to "single" without invalidating the receipt digest. When <code>signature_policy="dual"</code>, each <code>attestations[*].signatures</code> array MUST contain at minimum two entries with distinct <code>role</code> values, at least one of which MUST be "enclave" and at least one of which MUST be "hypervisor" or "monitor"; the two signing keys MUST be resident in independent trust domains (e.g., an enclave attestation key vs. a hypervisor-held key rooted in a separate certificate chain)—if both keys are derived from the same root or held in the same memory space, dual-signature provides no meaningful security uplift. Verifiers MUST reject attestation entries that do not satisfy the cardinality and role-distinctness requirements for the declared <code>signature_policy</code>. When <code>signature_policy="single"</code>, <code>minItems ≥ 1</code> applies; however, receipts with <code>signature_policy="single"</code> SHOULD be flagged as reduced-assurance by verifiers and MUST NOT be accepted by verifiers configured for dual-signature enforcement.</p>
attestation_mode	string	Y	<p>Attestation emission mode. Enum: "periodic" (heartbeat attestations) or "start_stop" (instantiation + termination only).</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
<code>attestation_policy.tau_ms</code>	integer	C	Required if <code>attestation_mode="periodic"</code> . Cadence threshold τ (ms) used to detect missed heartbeats. Constraint: integer ≥ 1 . Recommended $\tau \leq 500$ ms (optional ≤ 1000 ms).
<code>attestation_chain_root</code>	string	Y	Commitment to the ordered attestation chain. MUST be covered by <code>receipt_digest</code> . Recommended construction: form the JSON array of strings <code>[attestations[0].state_digest, ..., attestations[n-1].state_digest]</code> using the exact <code>state_digest</code> strings from the ordered chain (from inline <code>attestations[*].state_digest</code> when <code>attestations</code> is present; otherwise from the externally stored <code>attestation_bundle</code> referenced by <code>attestation_bundle_ref</code>). Canonicalize that array with RFC 8785 JCS, encode as UTF-8 bytes, then hash. Value is <code><hash-alg>:<digest-hex></code> where <code><digest-hex></code> is exactly 64 lowercase hex characters (so <code><hash-alg></code> denotes a 256-bit hash). Suggested pattern: <code>^[a-z0-9-]+:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code> . Each <code>state_digest</code> string is a fixed-format value of the form <code>sha256:<64hex></code> (≈ 75 bytes), so the JCS array serialization is deterministic and unambiguous—no length-extension or delimiter-confusion risk arises.

Design note (`attestation_chain_root`): This is a flat (non-Merkle) commitment over the full ordered chain; verifiers *MUST* buffer the entire attestation chain before checking `attestation_chain_root`, as incremental/streaming verification of individual entries is not supported by this construction. The flat commitment imposes a concrete verification cost linear in the chain length: at the `maxItems` limit of 10,000 entries the JCS array input is ≈ 750 KB; for a representative periodic-mode session at $\tau = 500$ ms running for 30 minutes ($\approx 3,600$ entries) it is ≈ 270 KB. Verifiers must allocate memory for the full serialized array and compute a single hash pass, with no opportunity for early rejection of individual entries. Implementations should account for these memory and latency requirements, particularly under adversarial conditions where a receipt may declare the maximum chain length. A future EPR version may introduce a Merkle-chain construction to enable incremental verification and sublinear proof sizes for individual attestation entries.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestation_bundle_digest	string	C	Required when <code>attestations</code> is absent; also required when <code>receipt_profile="EPR-1.1-compact"</code> (even if <code>attestations</code> is present inline, serving as a cross-check that the inline and external representations are byte-identical). Commitment to the <i>canonical attestation bundle</i> . Compute RFC 8785 JCS over <code>attestation_bundle</code> → UTF-8 bytes → SHA-256; encode as <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> . Pattern: <code>^sha256:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code> . See normative details below.

attestation_bundle_digest — **normative requirements.** The `attestation_bundle` is defined as a JSON object with exactly three keys: `"attestations"`, `"certs"`, and `"key_material_by_kid"`. All three keys **MUST** be present regardless of `receipt_profile`; the canonical key order is enforced by JCS (RFC 8785). When computing `attestation_bundle_digest`: `"attestations"` **MUST** contain the full ordered attestation array; `"certs"` **MUST** contain the complete certificate bag (all leaf certificates, all intermediates); `"key_material_by_kid"` **MUST** contain the complete key-to-certificate mapping. In `"EPR-1.1-compact"` profile, the receipt JSON itself **MAY** omit `certs` and `key_material_by_kid` (they are provided out-of-band), but `attestation_bundle_digest` **MUST** still be computed over the full three-key bundle object. The entity that computes `attestation_bundle_digest` (typically the UMCEE or receipt issuer) **MUST** have access to all three components at computation time. The canonical bytes of this full bundle object are what **MUST** be stored at `attestation_bundle_ref` and what verifiers **MUST** fetch and hash. If `attestations` and/or `certs` and/or `key_material_by_kid` are present inline, verifier **MUST** recompute `attestation_bundle_digest` from the inline values and reject on mismatch. *Split-world prevention*: if a verifier receives a compact receipt with `attestation_bundle_digest` and then fetches the bundle from `attestation_bundle_ref`, the verifier **MUST** verify that any `certs` or `key_material_by_kid` provided via other out-of-band channels are byte-identical to those in the fetched bundle; a mismatch **MUST** cause rejection to prevent split-world attacks where different verifiers see different certificate sets.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestation_bundle_ref	string (uri)	O	Optional URI where the <i>canonical bytes</i> of the <code>attestation_bundle</code> can be fetched. <code>format: uri</code> . Recommended: <code>https</code> scheme and content-addressed storage. The fetched bytes MUST be exactly the RFC 8785 JCS canonical JSON text bytes of the full three-key bundle object (<code>"attestations"</code> , <code>"certs"</code> , <code>"key_material_by_kid"</code>) used to compute <code>attestation_bundle_digest</code> (i.e., <code>UTF8(JCS(attestation_bundle))</code>); verifiers MUST hash fetched bytes as-is (MUST NOT parse and reserialize) and reject on mismatch. Verifiers MUST enforce fetch size limits and timeouts consistent with configured limits (e.g., a maximum bundle size derived from the <code>attestations maxItems</code> limit).
attestations	array<object>	C	Ordered list of attestation entries (ascending by time/counter). Required iff <code>receipt_profile="EPR-1.1-full"</code> . In <code>"EPR-1.1-compact"</code> profile, MAY be omitted; if omitted, <code>attestation_bundle_digest</code> MUST be present and independent verification requires access to the external bundle (via <code>attestation_bundle_ref</code> or out-of-band). MUST start with <code>kind="start"</code> and end with <code>kind="stop"</code> . <code>minItems</code> ≥ 2 . If <code>attestation_mode="start_stop"</code> , MUST contain exactly two entries: start then stop. Implementations MUST enforce a maximum chain length (<code>maxItems</code>) to prevent resource exhaustion; recommended $\leq 10,000$ entries (configurable), and verifiers SHOULD reject receipts exceeding configured limits.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].kind	string	Y	Attestation phase. Enum: "start", "heartbeat", "stop". In <code>attestation_mode="start_stop"</code> , only "start" and "stop" appear.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].ts	string (date-time)	Y	<p>Attestation timestamp in RFC 3339 / ISO 8601 (<code>format: date-time</code>).</p> <p>Advisory/auditing only: <code>ts</code> is NOT the authoritative ordering indicator; <code>freshness_counter</code> is the sole authoritative field for chain ordering and continuity verification (see <code>freshness_counter</code>). Timestamps SHOULD be monotonically non-decreasing with respect to <code>freshness_counter</code> order, but verifiers MUST NOT reject a receipt solely on the basis of non-monotonic or implausible <code>ts</code> values, since real-world clock drift, NTP corrections, and leap-second adjustments can produce legitimate out-of-order or duplicate wall-clock readings. Timestamp-range validation (SHOULD): although <code>ts</code> is advisory, verifiers SHOULD apply a configurable plausibility window (e.g., reject entries whose <code>ts</code> falls more than $\pm W$ seconds from the verifier's expected wall-clock range for the session, where W accounts for maximum expected clock skew plus session duration). This defends against a compromised enclave that increments <code>freshness_counter</code> correctly but sets timestamps arbitrarily far in the past or future to mislead auditors. Timestamp-range validation is not a substitute for <code>freshness_counter</code> verification and MUST NOT be used to override a passing counter-based continuity check; it is an additional auditing heuristic. Verifiers that enforce timestamp-range checks SHOULD log violations as warnings (not hard failures) unless deployment policy explicitly upgrades them to rejection criteria.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*]. freshness_counter	integer	Y	<p>Monotonic freshness indicator and the sole authoritative ordering field for the attestation chain. All chain ordering, continuity, and freshness verification MUST be performed against freshness_counter; the co-present ts field is advisory and MUST NOT be used as a substitute for counter-based checks (see attestations[*].ts). MUST be strictly increasing across the ordered attestation chain: each entry's freshness_counter MUST be strictly greater than the preceding entry's value; duplicate or non-increasing values MUST cause rejection. In "periodic" mode, adjacent entries SHOULD increment by exactly 1; any gap (i.e., $\text{freshness_counter}[i] - \text{freshness_counter}[i-1] > 1$) indicates one or more missed heartbeats and MUST trigger egress refusal. In "start_stop" mode, the stop entry's counter MUST be greater than the start entry's counter; the magnitude of the gap is not constrained. Threat-model note: a compromised enclave that controls both ts and freshness_counter can produce syntactically valid chains with misleading timestamps (e.g., timestamps far in the future while counters increment normally). Counter-based verification detects continuity violations but cannot detect wall-clock manipulation; deployments requiring wall-clock integrity SHOULD layer timestamp-range validation (see attestations[*].ts) and SHOULD cross-reference issued_at and external timing signals where available. Full clock-integrity guarantees require a trusted time source (e.g., platform secure timers or an external timestamping authority), which is outside the scope of EPR-1.1.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].component	string	Y	Component label for this attestation entry producer (distinct from the receipt issuer), e.g., "leaf". Non-empty string.
attestations[*].platform	string	Y	Platform identifier/namespace (e.g., "AWS-NITRO", "AMD-SEV-SNP", "INTEL-TDX"). Non-empty string.
attestations[*].evidence_format	string	Y	Platform evidence format identifier. Determines the evidence encoding profile and the non-binding convention used to verify this entry's evidence blob. Defined values: "amd-sev-snp-report", "intel-tdx-quote", "aws-nitro-doc", "tpm2-quote". Verifiers MUST use this field (not platform) to select the evidence-binding profile and per-format size limits. Implementations MAY register additional format identifiers; verifiers MUST reject unrecognized values unless the deployment profile explicitly extends the registry. Non-empty string.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].state_digest	string	Y	<p>Algorithm-qualified digest of the canonical attested state claims for this entry. Let <code>state_claims</code> be a JSON object with a fixed, deterministic schema constructed for this attestation entry (see Appendix B for the normative field list and canonical construction procedure). Compute <code>state_digest = sha256(JCS(state_claims))</code>: apply RFC 8785 JCS to <code>state_claims</code>, encode the canonicalized JSON text as UTF-8 bytes, then hash with SHA-256; encode as <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code>. In all attestations, <code>state_claims</code> MUST include <code>policy_state_digest</code>, <code>attestations[*].freshness_counter</code>, and <code>platform_report.image_digest</code>; if <code>dp_tuple.enabled=true</code>, it MUST also include <code>dp_tuple.tuple_digest</code>. If <code>kind="stop"</code> (terminal), <code>state_claims</code> MUST additionally include (when <code>dp_tuple.enabled=true</code>) <code>update_digest</code>, MUST include <code>response_ciphertext_digest</code> when <code>decision="RELEASE"</code> (and MUST omit it when <code>decision="WITHHOLD"</code>), and MUST include <code>zeroization_report_digest</code> and <code>teardown_digest</code>. For non-terminal attestations (<code>kind="start"</code> or <code>kind="heartbeat"</code>), <code>state_claims</code> MUST NOT include <code>update_digest</code>, <code>response_ciphertext_digest</code>, <code>zeroization_report_digest</code>, or <code>teardown_digest</code>. Define the domain-separated signing input <code>sig_input = UTF8("EPR-1.1/state_digest/") UTF8(state_digest)</code> and compute all signatures in <code>attestations[*].signatures[*].sig</code> over <code>sig_input</code> bytes. The domain-separation prefix is version-locked (see <code>receipt_signature</code>). Pattern: <code>^sha256:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code>.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*]. evidence_digest	string	Y	<p>Digest commitment to the platform attestation evidence blob (e.g., SNP report, TDX quote, Nitro attestation document, TPM quote) in its profile-defined canonical encoding. Compute SHA-256 over the raw evidence bytes (not over a base64 text form) and encode as <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code>. Evidence MUST cryptographically bind (i) the freshness challenge <code>freshness.nonce</code> and (ii) this entry's <code>state_digest</code> (e.g., via <code>report-data/user-data</code>) to prevent replay and mix-and-match. The binding convention (whether the nonce is bound as raw <code>nonce_bytes</code> or as <code>sha256(nonce_bytes)</code>, and how <code>state_digest</code> is packed alongside) is determined by the <code>evidence_format</code> value of this attestation entry; compliant verifiers MUST implement each platform-specific binding profile. The normative per-platform conventions are defined in the <code>freshness.nonce</code> field description and in the platform evidence binding profiles specification (Appendix D): e.g., SNP/TDX use <code>sha256(nonce_bytes) state_digest_bytes</code> in 64-byte <code>report-data</code>; Nitro uses raw <code>nonce_bytes state_digest_bytes</code> in variable-length <code>user-data</code>. If <code>attestations[*].evidence</code> is present, verifier MUST <code>base64url-decode</code> to evidence bytes and check it hashes to <code>evidence_digest</code>. If <code>attestations[*].evidence_ref</code> is present, verifier fetches evidence bytes from the URI and checks the hash matches. If neither is present, independent verification requires out-of-band access to the evidence bytes.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].evidence	string	O	Optional inline attestation evidence bytes. RFC 4648 base64url without padding of the raw evidence bytes. Verifier MUST decode to bytes and verify <code>sha256(evidence_bytes)</code> matches <code>attestations[*].evidence_digest</code> . Implementations MUST enforce a maximum decoded evidence size per <code>evidence_format</code> to prevent DoS. Normative defaults: \leq 256 KB for "amd-sev-snp-report", "intel-tdx-quote", and "tpm2-quote"; \leq 512 KB for "aws-nitro-doc" (Nitro attestation documents embed CA bundles and multiple PCRs, routinely exceeding 256 KB). These defaults are normative unless a deployment profile explicitly overrides them; verifiers SHOULD reject evidence exceeding the applicable per-format limit. Deployment profiles that override the defaults MUST publish their configured per-format limits in a machine-readable configuration document so that all conformant verifiers in the deployment enforce identical thresholds; failure to do so creates an interoperability risk where two conformant verifiers accept or reject the same receipt depending on locally configured limits.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].evidence_ref	string (uri)	O	Optional URI where the evidence bytes can be fetched (content-addressed storage recommended). format: uri. Recommended: https scheme only. The fetched bytes MUST be the profile-defined canonical evidence bytes indicated by <code>attestations[*].evidence_format</code> (i.e., the exact bytes hashed for <code>attestations[*].evidence_digest</code>); verifiers MUST hash fetched bytes as-is (MUST NOT parse and re-serialize). Verifier fetches evidence bytes and checks they hash to <code>attestations[*].evidence_digest</code> . If both <code>attestations[*].evidence</code> and <code>attestations[*].evidence_ref</code> are present, they MUST refer to identical bytes. Verifiers MUST enforce fetch size limits and timeouts per <code>evidence_format</code> (normative defaults: ≤ 256 KB for SNP/TDX/TPM; ≤ 512 KB for Nitro). As with inline evidence, these defaults are normative unless a deployment profile explicitly publishes overriding limits; see <code>attestations[*].evidence</code> for the interoperability requirement.
attestations[*].kid	string	O	Key identifier for the signing key used for this attestation entry (if needed to disambiguate within <code>key_material_by_kid</code>).

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
attestations[*].signatures	array<object>	Y	List of signatures over the identical <code>state_digest</code> . Cardinality and role requirements are governed by <code>signature_policy</code> (see above). When <code>signature_policy="dual"</code> : <code>minItems ≥ 2</code> ; MUST include at least one entry with <code>role="enclave"</code> and at least one entry with <code>role ∈ {"hypervisor", "monitor"}</code> ; the two signing keys MUST be resident in independent trust domains (see <code>signature_policy</code>). When <code>signature_policy="single"</code> : <code>minItems ≥ 1</code> . Implementations SHOULD enforce <code>maxItems</code> (e.g., <code>≤ 8</code>) to prevent DoS.
attestations[*].signatures[*].role	string	Y	Signature origin role. Enum: <code>"enclave", "hypervisor", "monitor"</code> (extendable).
attestations[*].signatures[*].sig	string	Y	Signature over the domain-separated signing input for this attestation entry's <code>state_digest</code> . Define <code>sig_input = UTF8("EPR-1.1/state_digest/") UTF8(attestations[*].state_digest)</code> and sign <code>sig_input</code> bytes. Recommended profiles: <code>ecdsa-p256-sha256</code> (ECDSA P-256 with SHA-256) or <code>ecdsa-p384-sha384</code> (ECDSA P-384 with SHA-384). Example encoding: <code>ecdsa-p384-sha384:<b64url(der-sig)></code> (DER-encoded signature bytes base64url-encoded, RFC 4648 no padding). Suggested pattern: <code>^(ecdsa-p256-sha256 ecdsa-p384-sha384):[A-Za-z0-9_-]+\$</code> . Implementations SHOULD enforce a maximum encoded signature length (e.g., <code>≤ 512</code> chars) to prevent DoS.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
certs	array<string>	C	Certificate bundle (PEM) for verifying <code>receipt_signature</code> and <code>attestations[*].signatures[*].sig</code> . This is an unordered certificate <i>bag</i> (may include multiple leaf certificates—one per signer—plus intermediates), not a single linear chain. Required iff <code>receipt_profile="EPR-1.1-full"</code> (for self-contained, third-party verification). In "EPR-1.1-compact" profile, MAY be omitted; if omitted, verifiers MUST resolve signing keys via configured trust anchors / out-of-band distribution and MAY use <code>attestation_bundle_ref</code> to retrieve certificate material. <code>minItems</code> ≥ 1 . Implementations MUST enforce <code>maxItems</code> (recommended ≤ 32) and per-entry maximum length (e.g., ≤ 8 KB) to prevent DoS.
key_material_by_kid	object	C	Mapping from key identifiers (<code>kid</code> values) to verification material/hints, enabling deterministic resolution of signing keys in multi-signer receipts. Required iff <code>receipt_profile="EPR-1.1-full"</code> . Object keys are <code>kid</code> strings; each value MUST identify a leaf certificate present in <code>certs</code> (recommended: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> over DER certificate bytes) or provide a profile-defined public key encoding. Verifiers use this mapping to select the correct public key, then validate certificate paths to configured trust anchors. Implementations MUST enforce maximum map size (recommended ≤ 32 entries) and per-entry length limits to prevent DoS.
Platform measurement report			
platform_report	object	Y	Platform measurement report for the runtime/image being attested. MUST be bound into <code>state_digest</code> (directly or via digest).

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
platform_report.platform	string	Y	Platform identifier (should match attestation platform namespace). Non-empty string.
platform_report.image_digest	string	Y	Digest of the runtime image / build artifact in a reproducible, profile-defined canonical encoding. MUST be SHA-256 over canonical <code>image_bytes</code> as defined by the platform measurement profile (e.g., OCI image manifest bytes for container deployments, or the measured VM/enclave image bytes for a given platform). MUST NOT be a mutable tag (e.g., <code>latest</code>). Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> . Pattern: <code>^sha256:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code> .
platform_report.cadence_ms	integer	C	Required iff <code>attestation_mode="periodic"</code> . Reporting/sampling cadence in milliseconds for freshness/continuity evidence. Constraint: integer ≥ 1 . If <code>attestation_mode="periodic"</code> , SHOULD satisfy <code>platform_report.cadence_ms \leq attestation_policy.tau_ms</code> . If <code>attestation_mode="start_stop"</code> , MAY be omitted; if present, it is interpreted as an internal sampling cadence used to generate the start/stop evidence.
platform_report.config_digest	string	O	Optional digest committing to runtime configuration relevant to write-blocking / I/O guards / DMA guards (IOMMU), etc. Algorithm-qualified <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> .
platform_report.allowlist_ref	string	O	Optional reference to a reproducible-build allow-list entry/version against which <code>image_digest</code> is validated.

Policy binding

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
network_policy	array<string>	Y	Declared policy tokens (e.g., ["self-origin"]). Items are non-empty strings. For deterministic receipts, tokens SHOULD be unique and sorted lexicographically. Implementations SHOULD enforce <code>maxItems</code> (recommended ≤ 64) and a per-token length limit (e.g., ≤ 64 chars) to prevent DoS. These tokens are advisory; the authoritative policy is committed by <code>policy_state_digest</code> .
policy_state_digest	string	Y	Digest commitment to the complete policy state/configuration (e.g., egress allowlist, write-blocking rules, TTL, model/route profile, DP budget thresholds). Let <code>policy_state</code> be the canonical JSON policy object (see the policy canonicalization specification in Appendix D). Compute RFC 8785 JCS over <code>policy_state</code> \rightarrow UTF-8 bytes \rightarrow SHA-256. Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> . Pattern: <code>^sha256:[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code> .
Differential privacy tuple Γ (mechanism-specific; bound into state_digest)			

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
dp_tuple	object	Y	<p>DP tuple Γ for the session/update. In inference-only mode, set <code>dp_tuple.enabled=false</code> and omit all conditional DP fields.</p> <p>Decimal encoding: all <code>string</code> (<code>decimal</code>) values within <code>dp_tuple</code> MUST be canonical base-10 strings with no exponent notation, no leading <code>+</code>, and no leading zeros (except <code>"0"</code>). If a fractional part is present, it MUST NOT end in <code>0</code>; if the value is integral, it MUST be encoded without a decimal point. Suggested pattern: <code>^(0 [1-9][0-9]*)(\.[0-9]*[1-9])?\$</code> (non-canonical examples: <code>"01"</code>, <code>"1.0"</code>, <code>"1.00"</code>). Encoding vs. domain note: the canonical decimal pattern permits the string <code>"0"</code>, but every DP parameter that uses this encoding is independently constrained to be strictly positive ($C > 0$, $S > 0$, $\sigma > 0$, $b > 0$, $\varepsilon > 0$, $\rho > 0$, etc.). Verifiers MUST apply <i>both</i> the syntactic format check <i>and</i> the per-field domain constraint; a value that passes the regex but violates the domain bound (e.g., <code>clip.bound="0"</code>) MUST be rejected.</p>
dp_tuple.enabled	boolean	Y	<p><code>true</code> iff an update artifact is produced/transmitted; <code>false</code> for inference-only mode.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
dp_tuple.mech	string	C	Required if enabled=true. Enum: "gaussian", "laplace", "zcdp_gaussian", "rdp_subsampled_gaussian". Verifiers MUST enforce mech-guarantee.type consistency: "laplace" \Rightarrow guarantee.type="pure_dp" and guarantee.delta="0"; "gaussian" \Rightarrow guarantee.type="approx_dp"; "zcdp_gaussian" \Rightarrow guarantee.type="zcdp"; "rdp_subsampled_gaussian" \Rightarrow guarantee.type="rdp". Mechanism-specific required parameters: Laplace requires params.b; Gaussian requires params.sigma; RDP requires params.noise_multiplier and accountant.*.
dp_tuple.adjacency	string	C	Required if enabled. Defines neighboring datasets for sensitivity. Enum: "add_remove" or "replace_one".
dp_tuple.clip.norm	string	C	Required if enabled. Norm used for per-record clipping. Enum: "l2" or "l1". Mechanism constraints: Gaussian/zCDP/RDP require "l2"; Laplace SHOULD use "l1".
dp_tuple.clip.bound	string (decimal)	C	Required if enabled. Per-record clipping bound $C > 0$ (decimal string).
dp_tuple.sensitivity.norm	string	C	Required if enabled. Norm under which sensitivity S is defined. MUST match clip.norm when sensitivity.source="derived_from_clip".

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
dp_tuple.sensitivity.bound	string (decimal)	C	Required if enabled. Sensitivity bound $S > 0$ (decimal string). If <code>sensitivity.source="derived_from_clip"</code> , the verifier enforces the derivation rule associated with the declared <code>calibration.rule</code> and <code>adjacency</code> . The <i>default</i> derivation (applicable to standard per-example gradient clipping under SGD-family optimizers) is: $S = C$ for <code>add_remove</code> ; $S = 2C$ for <code>replace_one</code> . Calibration rules that imply a different sensitivity model (e.g., record-level vs. example-level clipping, or non-gradient update mechanisms) MUST define their own $S(C, adjacency)$ mapping in the calibration-rule specification; verifiers MUST dispatch to the derivation function registered for the active <code>calibration.rule</code> .
dp_tuple.sensitivity.source	string	C	Required if enabled. Enum: <code>"derived_from_clip"</code> or <code>"explicit"</code> .
dp_tuple.guarantee.type	string	C	Required if enabled. Enum: <code>"approx_dp"</code> ((ϵ, δ) -DP), <code>"pure_dp"</code> (ϵ -DP), <code>"zcdp"</code> (ρ -zCDP), or <code>"rdp"</code> (Rényi DP). MUST be consistent with <code>dp_tuple.mech: laplace\Leftrightarrowpure_dp, gaussian\Leftrightarrowapprox_dp, zcdp_gaussian\Leftrightarrowzcdp, rdp_subsampled_gaussian\Leftrightarrowrdp</code> .
dp_tuple.guarantee.epsilon	string (decimal)	C	Required when <code>guarantee.type</code> is <code>"approx_dp"</code> or <code>"pure_dp"</code> . Must parse to $\epsilon > 0$.
dp_tuple.guarantee.delta	string (decimal)	C	Required when <code>guarantee.type</code> is <code>"approx_dp"</code> or <code>"pure_dp"</code> . MUST equal <code>"0"</code> when <code>guarantee.type="pure_dp"</code> . When <code>guarantee.type="approx_dp"</code> , must parse to $0 < \delta < 1$. For <code>guarantee.type</code> in <code>{"zcdp", "rdp"}</code> , this optional field is the δ used to convert the guarantee to (ϵ, δ) for policy checks; if present, must parse to $0 < \delta < 1$.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
dp_tuple.guarantee.rho	string (decimal)	C	Required when <code>guarantee.type="zcdp"</code> . Must parse to $\rho > 0$.
dp_tuple.accountant.type	string	C	Required when <code>mech="rdp_subsampled_gaussian"</code> (or <code>guarantee.type="rdp"</code>). Enum: <code>"rdp"</code> (extendable).
dp_tuple.accountant.sample_rate	string (decimal)	C	Required for RDP accountant. Sampling rate γ (decimal string). Must satisfy $0 < \gamma \leq 1$.
dp_tuple.accountant.rounds	integer	C	Required for RDP accountant. Number of composition rounds $T \geq 1$.
dp_tuple.calibration.rule	string	C	Required if enabled. Mechanism-specific calibration/accounting rule identifier. Examples: Gaussian: <code>"dwork_roth_1p25"</code> [52] (enforce $\sigma \geq S\sqrt{2\ln(1.25/\delta)}/\epsilon$) or <code>"analytic_gaussian"</code> ; Laplace: <code>"laplace_scale"</code> (enforce $b \geq S/\epsilon$ and $\delta = 0$); zCDP: <code>"zcdp_rho"</code> (convert via $\epsilon(\delta) = \rho + 2\sqrt{\rho\ln(1/\delta)}$); RDP: <code>"rdp_subsampled_gaussian_v1"</code> (deterministic accountant). Each calibration rule also defines the sensitivity derivation function $S(C, \text{adjacency})$ used when <code>sensitivity.source="derived_from_clip"</code> (see <code>sensitivity.bound</code>).
dp_tuple.params.sigma	string (decimal)	C	Required for <code>mech="gaussian"</code> and recommended for <code>mech="zcdp_gaussian"</code> . Gaussian noise stddev $\sigma > 0$ (decimal string). If <code>calibration.rule="dwork_roth_1p25"</code> , verifier MUST enforce $\sigma \geq S\sqrt{2\ln(1.25/\delta)}/\epsilon$.
dp_tuple.params.b	string (decimal)	C	Required for <code>mech="laplace"</code> . Laplace scale $b > 0$ (decimal string). Verifier MUST enforce $b \geq S/\epsilon$ and <code>guarantee.delta="0"</code> .
dp_tuple.params.noise_multiplier	string (decimal)	C	Required for <code>mech="rdp_subsampled_gaussian"</code> . Noise multiplier $z > 0$ (decimal string). Interpreted as $\sigma = z \cdot C$ (where $C = \text{clip.bound}$) unless the spec defines an alternate convention.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
dp_tuple.rdp_curve	array<object>	O	Optional explicit RDP curve points included in Γ (supports independent Rényi DP accounting verification). If present, verifier/aggregator SHOULD check consistency with <code>accountant.*</code> and <code>params.noise_multiplier</code> under the declared <code>calibration.rule</code> . For deterministic receipts, points MUST have unique <code>alpha</code> values and SHOULD be sorted by increasing numeric <code>alpha</code> ; verifiers SHOULD reject duplicate <code>alpha</code> . Implementations SHOULD enforce <code>maxItems</code> (recommended ≤ 64) to prevent DoS.
dp_tuple.rdp_curve[*].alpha	string (decimal)	C	Required if <code>rdp_curve</code> present. Rényi order $\alpha > 1$ (decimal string). MUST be unique within <code>rdp_curve</code> .
dp_tuple.rdp_curve[*].eps_alpha	string (decimal)	C	Required if <code>rdp_curve</code> present. RDP value $\varepsilon_\alpha \geq 0$ (decimal string).
dp_tuple.tuple_digest	string	C	Required if <code>enabled=true</code> . Digest of canonicalized <code>dp_tuple</code> (excluding <code>tuple_digest</code> itself). Algorithm-qualified <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> . MUST be committed by <code>attestations[*].state_digest</code> to prevent swapping Γ across updates.
Update / teardown commitments (H(U) safeguard; zeroization report)			

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
update_digest	string	C	<p>Required iff <code>dp_tuple.enabled=true</code>. Commitment to the transmitted update artifact U (e.g., DP-noised update $\hat{\Delta}$). Define <code>update_container</code> as a canonical container describing the update (see the update encoding specification in Appendix D) with fields <code>format</code>, <code>shape</code>, <code>dtype</code>, and <code>payload.bytes</code>, where <code>payload.bytes</code> are the raw bytes of U (not a base64 text form). Compute <code>update_bytes</code> as the CBOR Preferred Serialization (RFC 8949, §4.2.2) of <code>update_container</code>, then <code>update_digest = sha256(update_bytes)</code>. Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code>. Note: CBOR is used here (rather than JCS used elsewhere in the receipt) because the update payload contains binary tensor data that CBOR encodes natively, avoiding the overhead and ambiguity of base64-in-JSON; see the update encoding specification in Appendix D for the full rationale and CBOR container schema.</p> <p>Implementation note: the required deterministic CBOR encoding profile is RFC 8949 §4.2.2 (Preferred Serialization), which extends the Core Deterministic Encoding Requirements of §4.2.1 with unambiguous floating-point and integer encoding rules. Implementations MUST use a CBOR library that produces Preferred Serialization output; different “canonical” CBOR modes (e.g., Core Deterministic vs. Preferred Serialization vs. CTAP2) are not byte-identical, so using the wrong profile will produce a different <code>update_digest</code>. The terminal attestation MUST commit to <code>update_digest</code> (the $H(U)$ <i>safeguard</i>: the requirement that the cryptographic hash of the update artifact is bound into the terminal attestation’s <code>state_digest</code>, ensuring that the update payload cannot be swapped or tampered with after attestation without detection).</p>

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
zeroization_report_digest	string	Y	<p>Commitment to post-teardown zeroization via a canonical <code>zeroization_report</code> (not a hash of full RAM contents). This is a <i>receipt-level</i> field populated at receipt issuance time from the terminal attestation's committed <code>state_claims</code>; the terminal (<code>kind="stop"</code>) attestation's <code>state_claims</code> MUST include this value, and the receipt issuer copies it to the top level at finalization. For non-terminal attestation entries (<code>kind="start"</code> or <code>kind="heartbeat"</code>), this field MUST NOT appear in <code>state_claims</code>. Let <code>zeroization_report</code> be a canonical JSON object describing the zeroization procedure and scope (see the zeroization report specification in Appendix C; the full normative schema is reproduced there), including at minimum <code>session_id</code>, <code>memory_map_digest</code> (commitment to the regions claimed wiped), <code>wipe_algorithm_id</code> (e.g., <code>"memset_s_v1"</code>), optional <code>post_wipe_selftest</code>, and <code>ts_monotonic</code> if available. Compute <code>zeroization_report_digest = sha256(JCS(zeroization_report))</code>: RFC 8785 JCS → UTF-8 bytes → SHA-256. Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code>. Trust model: the trust anchor for zeroization is the attested code identity bound by <code>platform_report.image_digest</code>; the platform attestation evidence (binding <code>image_digest</code> via <code>state_digest</code>) guarantees that the measured code faithfully executes the declared wipe algorithm over the declared memory regions. The terminal attestation MUST commit to <code>zeroization_report_digest</code>.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
teardown_digest	string	Y	<p>Digest commitment to tear-down/finalization via a canonical tear-down report (not raw state). This is a <i>receipt-level</i> field populated at receipt issuance time from the terminal attestation's committed <code>state_claims</code>; the terminal (<code>kind="stop"</code>) attestation's <code>state_claims</code> MUST include this value, and the receipt issuer copies it to the top level at finalization. For non-terminal attestation entries (<code>kind="start"</code> or <code>kind="heartbeat"</code>), this field MUST NOT appear in <code>state_claims</code>. Let <code>teardown_report</code> be a canonical JSON object describing tear-down/finalization (see the tear-down report specification in Appendix D). Compute RFC 8785 JCS over <code>teardown_report</code> \rightarrow UTF-8 bytes \rightarrow SHA-256. Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code>. The terminal attestation MUST commit to <code>teardown_digest</code>.</p>
transcript_commitment	object	Y	<p>Channel transcript commitment object (NOT raw transcript). MUST be covered by <code>receipt_digest</code> (it is a top-level field not in the exclusion set <code>{receipt_digest, receipt_signature}</code>; stated explicitly here for implementer clarity given the security-critical nature of this binding). Let <code>transcript</code> be the transcript serialization described in the transcript serialization specification (Appendix D; recommended: an ordered JSON array of message objects), and define <code>transcript_bytes = UTF8(JCS(transcript))</code> (RFC 8785 JCS \rightarrow UTF-8 bytes). Commitment SHOULD be computed by the receipt issuer (UMCEE/Egress Gate) over the transcript bytes it observes; the receipt binds only this commitment, not the raw transcript.</p>

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
transcript_commitment. scheme	string	Y	Commitment scheme. Enum: "hmac-sha256" (RECOMMENDED) or "salted-sha256". Implementations SHOULD default to "hmac-sha256" unless the deployment requires third-party verifiability without selective key disclosure. Security note: "salted-sha256" is binding but not strongly hiding—because the salt is public, an adversary with access to the receipt can mount offline dictionary/brute-force attacks to recover low-entropy transcripts (e.g., short or templated exchanges). "hmac-sha256" with a secret key not disclosed to third parties (e.g., derived from a TLS exporter / session secret) provides stronger privacy-by-default. Note that "hmac-sha256" requires selective key disclosure (or a dedicated verification protocol) for third-party receipt verification, since the verifier must derive or receive K to check the commitment; this is an intentional privacy/verifiability trade-off.
transcript_commitment.value	string	Y	Commitment value as 64 lowercase hex characters. If <code>scheme="hmac-sha256"</code> , <code>value = hex(HMAC-SHA-256(K, transcript_bytes))</code> , where K is derived per <code>transcript_commitment.key_id</code> and the receipt issuer MUST compute the HMAC prior to signing. If <code>scheme="salted-sha256"</code> , let <code>salt_bytes</code> be the base64url-decoded <code>transcript_commitment.salt</code> and set <code>value = hex(SHA-256(salt_bytes transcript_bytes))</code> . Pattern: <code>^[0-9a-f]{64}\$</code> .

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
transcript_commitment. key_id	string	C	Required iff <code>scheme="hmac-sha256"</code> . Identifies/derives a session-bound secret key K used for the HMAC (key not included). Recommended: derive K from the mutually authenticated channel so both the regulated client and the receipt issuer (UM-CEE/Egress Gate) can compute it (e.g., TLS exporter); encode <code>key_id</code> as an unambiguous identifier such as <code>"tls-exporter:<b64url>"</code> or <code>"server-secret:<id>"</code> . The receipt issuer MUST compute and include <code>value</code> ; a regulated client that can derive K SHOULD verify <code>value</code> against its local transcript.
transcript_commitment.salt	string	C	Required iff <code>scheme="salted-sha256"</code> . Random salt (recommended 16–32 bytes) encoded as RFC 4648 base64url without padding. Verifier MUST decode to <code>salt.bytes</code> ; hashing MUST use decoded bytes (not the base64 text). MUST be covered by <code>receipt.digest</code> . Security note: because the salt is public, <code>"salted-sha256"</code> is not strongly hiding and may permit offline brute-force of guessable transcripts. Recommended: when using salted commitments, the receipt issuer (Egress Gate) computes <code>value</code> over the transcript bytes it observes and does not retain the raw transcript.

External inputs / connectors (hash-bound)

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
connector_selection	array<object>	Y	List of external inputs/connectors bound into the receipt via hashes. Can be empty; items are connector objects. Producers MUST sort items by name ascending (UTF-8 byte-order comparison), breaking ties by sha256 ascending (ASCII/hex byte-order comparison), to ensure deterministic receipt_digest computation across implementations; items MUST be unique under this composite key. Implementer note: “UTF-8 byte-order” means raw unsigned-byte lexicographic comparison of the UTF-8–encoded name strings (i.e., memcmp -order), <i>not</i> locale-sensitive or Unicode Collation Algorithm (UCA) order. For ASCII-only names the two coincide, but for names containing non-ASCII UTF-8 code units the sort order may differ from what locale-aware library routines (e.g., strcoll , Intl.Collator) produce. Implementations MUST use a byte-level comparator; using a locale-sensitive sort will produce non-deterministic orderings across platforms and will cause receipt_digest mismatches. Implementations SHOULD enforce maxItems (recommended ≤ 128) and per-item size limits to prevent DoS; for large input sets, include a single manifest object whose digest commits to the full set.
connector_selection[*].name	string	Y	Human-readable connector artifact name (e.g., filename). Non-empty string. (Security note: SHOULD be sanitized and SHOULD NOT contain PHI/PII.) Implementations SHOULD enforce a maximum length (recommended ≤ 256 chars) to prevent DoS and accidental leakage.
connector_selection[*].sha256	string	Y	SHA-256 digest of the connector artifact. 64 hex chars: $\^[0-9a-fA-F]{64}\$$.

Continued on next page

Field (JSON path)	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
Transparency + verification endpoint			
transparency_merkle_root	string or null	Y	Transparency commitment. This field is required (Y) but its value MAY be <code>null</code> ; omitting the field entirely from the receipt JSON is non-conformant—implementations MUST include the key with an explicit <code>null</code> value when no transparency commitment is available, ensuring the field is always present in the <code>receipt_digest</code> input. If non-null, the value MUST be an algorithm-qualified digest <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> (recommended).
verifier_url	string (uri)	Y	URL where the receipt can be verified/fetched (e.g., API endpoint). <code>format: uri</code> . Recommended: <code>https</code> scheme only.

B Attestation State Claims Specification

This appendix defines the normative attestation state claims specification. It defines the canonical JSON object `state_claims` whose digest is committed as `attestations[*].state_digest` in every attestation entry of an EPR-1.1 receipt.

B.1 Purpose

Each attestation entry (start, heartbeat, or stop) commits to a `state_digest` computed over a deterministic `state_claims` JSON object. The state claims encode the security-critical measurements that the verifier checks: policy configuration, chain freshness, platform identity, and (at termination) proof-of-zero and update binding. By defining a fixed schema, interoperable verifiers can recompute `state_digest` and reject any receipt where the attested state does not match.

B.2 Canonical Construction Procedure

1. Construct a JSON object `state_claims` with the fields listed in Table 5, populating each field from the corresponding runtime measurement.
2. Serialize the object using RFC 8785 JSON Canonicalization Scheme (JCS).
3. Encode the canonical JSON text as UTF-8 bytes.
4. Compute SHA-256 over those bytes.
5. Encode the result as `sha256:<64-lowercase-hex-characters>`.

The resulting string is the `state_digest` value for this attestation entry.

B.3 Normative Field List

Table 5: Attestation State Claims fields. Presence: A = all entries; A* = all entries when the corresponding receipt-level field is present (omitted otherwise); T = terminal (`kind="stop"`) only; T|DP = terminal and only when `dp_tuple.enabled=true`; T|R = terminal and only when `decision="RELEASE"`.

Field	Type	Presence	Semantics
<code>version</code>	string	A	Schema version. MUST equal "EPR-SC-1.1".
<code>session_id</code>	string	A	Copied from the receipt-level <code>session_id</code> .
<code>kind</code>	string	A	Attestation phase: "start", "heartbeat", or "stop". MUST match <code>attestations[*].kind</code> .
<code>freshness_counter</code>	integer	A	Copied from <code>attestations[*].freshness_counter</code> for this entry. Provides the monotonic freshness indicator inside the signed digest.
<code>policy_state_digest</code>	string	A	Copied from the receipt-level <code>policy_state_digest</code> . Binds every attestation entry to the session policy.
<code>platform_report.image_digest</code>	string	A	Copied from <code>platform_report.image_digest</code> . Binds the attested code identity into the state digest.
<code>platform_report.config_digest</code>	string	A*	Copied from the receipt-level <code>platform_report.config_digest</code> when that optional field is present; MUST be omitted from <code>state_claims</code> when the receipt-level field is absent. Commits to write-block and I/O-guard configuration.
<code>dp_tuple.tuple_digest</code>	string	A DP	Required in every entry when <code>dp_tuple.enabled=true</code> . Binds the DP parameters into each heartbeat so a verifier can detect mid-session parameter tampering.
<code>update_digest</code>	string	T DP	Required in terminal entry when <code>dp_tuple.enabled=true</code> . Commits $H(U)$ (the update artifact hash) into the terminal state digest (the $H(U)$ safeguard).

Continued on next page

Field	Type	Presence	Semantics
<code>response_ciphertext_digest</code>	string	T R	Required in terminal entry when <code>decision="RELEASE"</code> . MUST be omitted when <code>decision="WITHHOLD"</code> . Binds the released ciphertext into the terminal state.
<code>zeroization_report_digest</code>	string	T	Required in every terminal entry. Commits to the Zeroization Report (Appendix C), proving post-teardown memory wipe.
<code>teardown_digest</code>	string	T	Required in every terminal entry. Commits to the Teardown Report describing the finalization sequence.

B.4 Inclusion and Exclusion Rules

- **Non-terminal entries** (`kind="start"` or `kind="heartbeat"`) MUST NOT include `update_digest`, `response_ciphertext_digest`, `zeroization_report_digest`, or `teardown_digest`. The presence of any of these fields in a non-terminal `state_claims` object is a schema violation; verifiers MUST reject such entries.
- **Terminal entries** (`kind="stop"`) MUST include `zeroization_report_digest` and `teardown_digest` unconditionally. They MUST include `update_digest` when `dp_tuple.enabled=true`, and MUST include `response_ciphertext_digest` when `decision="RELEASE"`.
- Fields not listed in Table 5 MUST NOT appear in `state_claims`. Unknown fields cause non-deterministic JCS output and MUST be rejected.

B.5 Security Properties

The state claims schema provides three security properties that a verifier can check mechanically:

1. **Policy binding.** Every attestation entry commits to `policy_state_digest`, so a mid-session policy swap (e.g., relaxing egress rules) invalidates the chain.
2. **Code identity continuity.** `platform_report.image_digest` appears in every entry; live migration or hot-patching that changes the measured image produces a state-digest mismatch.
3. **Terminal completeness.** The terminal entry (and only the terminal entry) commits to zeroization, teardown, update hash, and (when applicable) ciphertext hash. A verifier that sees a `kind="stop"` entry missing any mandatory terminal field MUST reject the receipt.

C Zeroization Report Specification

This appendix defines the normative zeroization report specification. It defines the canonical JSON object `zeroization_report` whose digest is committed as `zeroization_report_digest` in the terminal attestation entry and at the receipt top level.

C.1 Purpose and Trust Model

The Zeroization Report provides a structured, machine-verifiable claim that the UMCEE performed a deterministic memory wipe before or concurrently with enclave/container destruction. It does *not* contain a hash of the full RAM contents (which would be impractical and leak information); instead it commits to:

- **Which regions** were wiped (a memory-map digest).
- **How** they were wiped (a declared algorithm identifier).
- **Optional self-test evidence** that the wipe completed (e.g., a post-wipe sampling check).

Trust anchor. The trust root for the zeroization claim is the attested code identity bound by `platform_report.image_digest`. The platform attestation evidence (which binds `image_digest` into `state_digest` via the attestation chain) guarantees that the measured code faithfully executes the declared wipe algorithm over the declared memory regions. A verifier trusts the zeroization report to the extent that it trusts the measured code image.

C.2 Normative Field List

Table 6: Zeroization Report fields. Req.: Y = required; O = optional.

Field	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
<code>version</code>	string	Y	Report version. MUST equal "EPR-ZR-1.1".
<code>session_id</code>	string	Y	Session identifier. MUST match the receipt-level <code>session_id</code> .
<code>memory_map_digest</code>	string	Y	SHA-256 digest of a canonical description of the memory regions claimed wiped. The canonical description is a JCS-serialized JSON array of region objects, each containing { <code>'base_addr'</code> : <code>'<hex>'</code> , <code>'length_bytes'</code> : <code><int></code> }, sorted ascending by <code>base_addr</code> . Format: <code>sha256:<64-lower-hex></code> . This field commits to the <i>scope</i> of the wipe without revealing memory contents.

Field	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
<code>wipe_algorithm_id</code>	string	Y	Identifier for the wipe procedure. Defined values: <code>"memset_s_v1"</code> (C11 <code>memset_s</code> or equivalent non-elided zero-fill), <code>"rep_stosb_v1"</code> (x86 REP STOSB hardware instruction), <code>"dc_zva_v1"</code> (ARM DC ZVA hardware zero-by-virtual-address), <code>"crypto_erase_v1"</code> (destroy in-memory AES key; see Shadow-Storage Controller). Implementations MAY register additional algorithm identifiers; verifiers MUST reject unrecognized identifiers unless the deployment profile explicitly extends the registry.
<code>wipe_pass_count</code>	integer	O	Number of overwrite passes (default: 1). Multi-pass is typically unnecessary for DRAM but may be required by certain compliance regimes.
<code>post_wipe_selftest</code>	object	O	Optional self-test evidence. If present, MUST contain <code>method</code> (enum: <code>"sample_zero_check"</code> , <code>"full_zero_check"</code>) and <code>result</code> (enum: <code>"pass"</code> , <code>"fail"</code>). <code>"sample_zero_check"</code> : the wipe code samples k random cache-line-aligned addresses from the wiped region and verifies all-zero; recommended $k \geq 64$. <code>"full_zero_check"</code> : the wipe code reads back the entire wiped region and verifies all-zero (higher assurance, higher latency). A <code>result="fail"</code> MUST cause the UMCEE to emit a <code>decision="WITHHOLD"</code> receipt and MUST NOT release outputs.
<code>ts_monotonic</code>	string	O	Monotonic timestamp (nanoseconds since boot or enclave start) at which the wipe completed. If the platform provides a trusted monotonic clock (e.g., RDTSC-anchored or secure-timer-backed), this field SHOULD be populated. Advisory only; see the threat-model note on clock integrity in the main specification.

Field	Type	Req.	Semantics / constraints
<code>shadow_storage_status</code>	string	O	Status of Shadow-Storage Controller cleanup. Enum: "not_applicable" (no shadow storage was mounted during this session), "shredded" (all shadow-storage pages were overwritten within the shred window), "crypto_erased" (the per-session AES key was destroyed, rendering shadow-storage contents unrecoverable). If the session used any RAM-backed file system (e.g., <code>tmpfs</code>), this field SHOULD be present.

C.3 Canonical Construction and Digest Computation

1. Construct a JSON object `zeroization_report` with the fields from Table 6.
2. Serialize using RFC 8785 JCS.
3. Encode as UTF-8 bytes.
4. Compute `zeroization_report_digest = sha256(<UTF-8 bytes>)`.
5. Encode as `sha256:<64-lower-hex>`.

C.4 Proof-of-Zero Construction

The “proof of zero” referenced in the main specification is constructed as follows:

1. The UMCEE pauses all payload threads.
2. The wipe routine (identified by `wipe_algorithm_id`) overwrites every byte in every region listed in the memory map.
3. If `post_wipe_selftest` is configured, the self-test executes and records `result`.
4. The `zeroization_report` object is constructed.
5. `zeroization_report_digest` is computed and included in the terminal `state_claims`.
6. The terminal attestation is signed (committing to the state claims that include the zeroization digest).
7. The enclave/container is destroyed.

Steps 2–6 execute atomically from the perspective of the attested code image: no payload code runs between the wipe and the terminal attestation signature. This ordering guarantee is enforced by the measured code identity (`image_digest`) and verified transitively by the attestation chain.

C.5 Verifier Checks

A conformant verifier MUST perform the following checks on the zeroization report:

1. `version` equals "EPR-ZR-1.1".
2. `session_id` matches the receipt-level `session_id`.
3. `wipe_algorithm_id` is a recognized algorithm in the verifier's registry.
4. If `post_wipe_selftest` is present, `result` equals "pass".
5. Recompute `zeroization_report_digest` from the report object and verify it matches the value committed in the terminal attestation's `state_digest`.

D Additional Normative Specifications

This appendix specifies the remaining normative schemas and encoding conventions referenced by the EPR-1.1 receipt schema and verification protocol. Together with the full schemas in Appendices B and C, these specifications are self-contained: they supply sufficient detail for independent review, verification, and implementation of every security-critical claim made in the body of this report. Future companion documents may expand on implementation guidance, edge-case handling, and platform-specific errata.

D.1 Platform Evidence Binding Profiles

The Platform Evidence Binding Profiles specification defines how the freshness challenge (`freshness.nonce`) and per-entry `state_digest` are packed into each platform's attestation evidence blob. The binding ensures that a verifier can confirm that a given attestation evidence document was produced for *this* session (nonce) and *this* state (digest), preventing replay and mix-and-match attacks.

Normative per-platform conventions. These conventions are already reproduced inline in the `freshness.nonce` field description of Table 2 (main text):

- **AMD SEV-SNP** ("amd-sev-snp-report"): 64-byte `REPORT_DATA = sha256(nonce_bytes) || state_digest_bytes` (32 + 32 bytes).
- **Intel TDX** ("intel-tdx-quote"): 64-byte `REPORTDATA = sha256(nonce_bytes) || state_digest_bytes` (32 + 32 bytes).
- **AWS Nitro** ("aws-nitro-doc"): variable-length `user_data = nonce_bytes || state_digest_bytes` (raw nonce, not hashed).
- **TPM 2.0** ("tpm2-quote"): `qualifyingData = sha256(nonce_bytes || state_digest_bytes)`.

Future companion documents may additionally define: (i) evidence-format string registry and extensibility rules, (ii) maximum evidence size defaults per format, and (iii) verifier implementation requirements for each platform's certificate/endorsement-key validation chain. The normative conventions required for independent verification are defined above.

D.2 Policy Canonicalization

The Policy Canonicalization specification defines the canonical JSON object `policy_state` whose SHA-256 digest is committed as `policy_state_digest` in the receipt.

Minimum required fields. The policy object MUST include at minimum:

- `egress_allowlist`: ordered list of permitted egress destinations (hostnames or CIDR blocks).
- `write_block_mode`: enum `{"deny_all_nv", "redirect_to_ramdisk"}`.
- `ttl_seconds`: maximum session lifetime.
- `attestation_mode`: `"periodic"` or `"start_stop"`.
- `attestation_cadence_ms`: (if periodic) cadence τ .
- `dp_budget`: (if learning enabled) `{max_epsilon, max_delta}`.
- `model_route`: model identifier / endpoint URI committed to policy.

Canonicalization. Apply RFC 8785 JCS to the policy object, encode as UTF-8 bytes, then SHA-256. Unknown fields MUST NOT appear; the schema is closed. The resulting digest is the `policy_state_digest`.

D.3 Update Encoding

The Update Encoding specification defines the canonical CBOR container `update_container` used to compute `update_digest` when `dp_tuple.enabled=true`.

Rationale for CBOR. The update payload contains binary tensor data (floating-point arrays). CBOR (RFC 8949) encodes binary natively, avoiding the overhead and round-trip ambiguity of base64-in-JSON.

Container schema. The CBOR map MUST contain exactly four keys:

- `format` (text string): tensor format identifier, e.g., `"numpy_f32"`, `"safetensors_f16"`.
- `shape` (array of unsigned integers): tensor dimensions.
- `dtype` (text string): element data type, e.g., `"float32"`, `"float16"`.
- `payload_bytes` (byte string): raw bytes of the update artifact U .

Deterministic encoding. CBOR Preferred Serialization (RFC 8949, §4.2.2) MUST be used. Different “canonical” CBOR modes (Core Deterministic, Preferred Serialization, CTAP2) are *not* byte-identical; using the wrong profile produces a different `update_digest`.

Digest computation. `update_digest = sha256(CBOR_Preferred_Serialize(update_container))`.

D.4 Teardown Report

The Teardown Report specification defines the canonical JSON object `teardown_report` committed via `teardown_digest` in the terminal attestation.

Minimum required fields.

- `version`: "EPR-TD-1.1".
- `session_id`: MUST match receipt-level session ID.
- `teardown_trigger`: enum {"normal_completion", "policy_violation", "heartbeat_timeout", "operator_kill"}.
- `egress_decision`: "RELEASE" or "WITHHOLD" (mirrors receipt-level decision).
- `zeroization_report_digest`: cross-reference to the zeroization report committed in the same terminal entry.
- `ts_teardown`: RFC 3339 timestamp of teardown initiation.

Canonicalization. RFC 8785 JCS → UTF-8 bytes → SHA-256.

D.5 Transcript Serialization

The Transcript Serialization specification defines the canonical format for the channel transcript committed via `transcript_commitment`.

Recommended format. An ordered JSON array of message objects, each containing:

- `role`: "user" or "assistant".
- `content`: UTF-8 string of the message text.
- `seq`: integer sequence number (1-indexed, monotonically increasing).

Canonicalization. `transcript_bytes = UTF8(JCS(transcript_array))`. The commitment is then computed per the scheme declared in `transcript_commitment.scheme` (HMAC-SHA-256 or salted-SHA-256).

Privacy note. The receipt binds only the *commitment* (a 256-bit value), not the raw transcript. When `scheme="hmac-sha256"`, a third-party verifier cannot recover the transcript without the session-derived key K .